

CommuniCity

Innovative Solutions Responding
to the Needs of Cities & Communities

D2.2 A process for incremental improvement and matching needs of local citizens and communities to solutions offered by technology providers

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CommuniCity

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GLOSSARY

Marginalised groups	Marginalised groups include a wide range of communities and individuals who face social, cultural, economic or political exclusion and often experience discrimination or disadvantage in society.
Challenge	A problem or issue in society that affects a particular section of the population and has complex social, economic and/or cultural dimensions. These challenges are caused by various factors such as inequality, injustice, discrimination, poverty, environmental degradation, health inequalities and cultural or political conflicts.
Challenge owner	A challenge owner is the individual, target group or organisation that has identified and proposed a problem to be solved.
Social impact	The effect of a solution in addressing social problems and creating positive change in society. It includes tangible and intangible outcomes that improve the lives of people, communities and the world.
Co-creation	A collaborative process in which all stakeholders are equal participants. This approach recognises that the end users of the product or service often have valuable insights and understanding of their own needs and preferences that can enhance the design and development process.

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Executive Summary

The deliverable “A process for incremental improvement and matching the needs of citizens to solutions of tech providers” is part of the European Horizon project CommuniCity. It outlines a process for collaborative incremental improvement, matching the needs of marginalised citizens with technological solutions. CommuniCity started by running pilots for marginalised groups with the cities Amsterdam, Porto and Helsinki, with a view to eventually running 100 pilots across Europe. The deliverable, a product of Work Package 2 on Ethical and Inclusive Engagement, addresses the social position of marginalised groups, emphasising technology's dual role to both exacerbate and alleviate their position in society. In this deliverable there is room for two types of interpretation: the adaptation of existing tech solutions to the needs of marginalised groups and the development of tech solutions tailored to these needs.

Interviews and workshops with key stakeholders - government entities, civil society organisations, marginalised groups, and tech companies - and the experience from the pilots, reveal four main bottlenecks hindering the development, implementation and adoption of tech solutions for marginalised groups:

1. Low awareness among stakeholders regarding the value of technology for social challenges.
2. Insufficient knowledge and understanding of the needs of marginalised groups among tech entities.
3. Lack of funding for the development and procurement of tech solutions.
4. Few sustainable opportunities for the implementation and maintenance of tech solutions by civil society organisations.

Marginalised groups, facing physical, mental, and social barriers, confront challenges such as disabilities, mental health issues, illiteracy, poverty, unemployment, immigration, or refugee status, and loneliness. While technological advancements have significantly improved the lives of physically and mentally challenged people, there is a gap in solutions addressing social challenges. Various tech solutions have put e-health on the map, such as apps to measure heart rate, saturation, blood pressure and fall detection. Social challenges however are more complex with sensitive underlayers, such as (sexual) abuse, exploitation, and discrimination are harder to address due to their sensitivity, requiring a deep understanding of the subject and a secure relationship with the target group.

CommuniCity underscores the importance of **co-creation** and social **impact** in engaging marginalised communities. The **impact** of technological solutions is delineated across three dimensions: individual, social and societal impact. **Co-creation** is a way of collaboration, where the target group actively participates from challenge identification to solution adoption. Co-creation relies on the idea that the ideal solution emerges through collaboration, combining the full knowledge and skills of all parties to address the issue and meet the target audience's needs. Social innovation through co-creation is also known as human-centred design. Involving those facing challenges daily, empowers them to be part of the solution, breaking the cycle of dependency and showcasing their ability to influence their circumstances.

To meet the needs for greater involvement in tech development and a better understanding of target groups and challenges, we propose a **process grounded in human-centred design** (design thinking). It addresses the second bottleneck - *Insufficient knowledge and understanding of the needs of marginalised groups among tech companies*. The process outlines six phases, ranging from identifying societal challenges to adopting the

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tech solution, emphasising the social nature of the issues faced by marginalised groups. Most of the phases are detailed with goals, descriptions, tips and (co-creation) methods.

The deliverable also provides a handle for incremental improvement, with a focus on continuously learning from the several rounds of open calls and pilots within CommuniCity. We emphasise the importance of creating a good understanding of impact and co-creation among project participants, offering suggestions such as workshops on co-creation and evaluating proposals with a focus on these criteria.

The other three bottlenecks were outside the scope of the deliverable but affect the process. These are the importance of awareness, funding, and implementation for developing tech solutions to address social challenges. While sustainable solutions weren't found during CommuniCity pilots, we present ideas and suggestions sourced from research on these bottlenecks. These ideas, yet to be fully developed, are proposed for discussion within CommuniCity, considering their alignment with future deliverables. The aim is to explore opportunities for implementation within broader European, national, or municipal programs, potentially paving the way for future research and projects.

A process is a practical way of working together. But the human side is at least as important. It takes genuine interest and empathy to really develop solutions that meet the needs of marginalised groups. The unique knowledge stemming from personal experiences like homelessness or discrimination, requires empathy for effective solution design. Despite existing collaboration guidelines, many projects fall short in investing time to understand marginalised groups authentically, often resulting in solutions developed without direct input. Our aim is that the process outlined in this deliverable will increase engagement and put the experiences and ideas of marginalised groups at the heart of technology solutions that truly meet their needs and improve their social position.

Introduction

The deliverable *A process for incremental improvement and matching the needs of citizens to solutions of tech providers* aims to provide a growing process of collaboration between the different parties working together to develop technological solutions to the challenges faced by marginalised groups. The European Horizon project CommuniCity¹, which is working on innovative solutions through open calls and pilots in collaboration with several European cities, is the umbrella within which this deliverable was created. As part of Work Package 2 *Ethical and Inclusive Engagement in Practice*, this deliverable provides context for the social position of marginalised groups, how technology increases their disadvantage in society, but can also improve their position. The process described contributes to improving this position through methods that allow tech companies to put themselves in the shoes of the target group, through co-creation, in order to develop technology that truly meets their needs.

Context and purpose of CommuniCity

The main goal within Community is to learn from the open calls and pilots in developing tech for the challenges of marginalised groups. These lessons, from both successes and failures, should be shared to advance the development of tech for social challenges of marginalised groups in general, in such a way that these solutions are increasingly responsive to their needs. However, there are limitations to the pilot environment which makes the situation less than ideal for the development of technology for marginalised groups. Each pilot period lasts five to six months within which the cooperating partners work towards a solution. €12.500 is available per pilot. Working with a target group in quite a disadvantaged position and with such delicate challenges requires time and money to run realistic and feasible pilots in which the challenge owner, the target group and the tech company can take real steps. Since learning is the main objective, it does not matter whether a final implementable solution is eventually developed. However, it is a more positive experience for the learning process and the participants if concrete steps can be taken, giving the participants a feeling that a useful solution is ultimately achievable. A complicated challenge and a target group that needs to share vulnerable and sensitive information requires mutual trust. It takes time to really understand the challenge before the design process can begin. This also limits the complexity of the challenge that can be addressed in the pilot environment. Not enough attention has been paid to this within CommuniCity yet. This deliverable will take a first step in defining a scope for marginalised groups and societal challenges within such a pilot environment. We look at this in more detail in Chapter 2. The frameworks in this document contain suggestions for incremental steps that can be taken to better understand the target groups and the challenges they face. These can be used to develop new conditions for the next pilot environment. These suggestions are developed further in section 5.2 on incremental improvement.

Marginalised groups

CommuniCity works with and for residents in a marginalised position. The terms of reference of the deliverable and the working title of CommuniCity still refer to communities and citizens. The programme focuses on a more specific target group. These are marginalised groups. The challenges for which a tech solution is sought are of a social nature. Residents in a marginalised position, due to factors usually beyond their control, do not have the same opportunities as other, more fortunate groups in society. Examples include the unemployed, refugees and others who are socially excluded. When developing solutions with and

¹ [CommuniCity](#)

for marginalised groups, it is important to understand their position and the challenges they face. This is why this deliverable looks in detail at marginalised groups.

Impact and co-creation

Impact and co-creation are highly valued within the CommuniCity pilots. These are two of the four criteria on which submissions to the challenges in the open calls are assessed. Matching the needs of citizens (read marginalised groups) is about impact and co-creation. Ultimately, CommuniCity wants to contribute with innovative solutions to make positive social change as an improvement in the position of marginalised groups. If we want to realise solutions that, as the deliverable describes, contribute to end-user needs, then impact is an important measure. To really understand marginalised groups and their challenges and put their needs at the centre of developing a solution then co-creation is a good tool. Therefore, impact and co-creation are important parts of this deliverable.

Main bottlenecks

From our research, we extracted the main bottlenecks that hinder development of appropriate tech solutions for marginalised groups. We identified four main bottlenecks. Absence of:

1. awareness of the value of tech for social challenges,
2. adequately tailored solutions to the needs of marginalised groups,
3. solutions for implementation and maintenance of tech,
4. finance opportunities to develop tech for marginalised target groups.

The second bottleneck aligns with the brief of this deliverable and the pilot context of CommuniCity. From there, we shaped the process. The other bottlenecks are just as important for the development of tech for marginalised groups. They could not be researched and 'solved' within the CommuniCity project, but they are worth exploring and developing further. We do address these bottlenecks in this deliverable and make proposals for further research and projects (chapter 6).

The process

The process described in this deliverable is divided into six phases: 1. Detecting challenges, 2. Articulating the needs, 3. Matching tech parties, 4. Development of the tech solution, 5. Implementation and Maintenance, 6. Adoption. The fourth phase is in turn divided into six different phases derived from the Design Thinking process. These are; Empathise, Define, Ideate, Prototype and Test. For each phase, the aim is stated, with a description, tips and co-creation methods appropriate for working with marginalised groups.

The deliverable can be interpreted in different ways. Matching needs to solutions can be understood as adapting existing tech solutions to the needs of specific target groups. The starting point in the design process is then the existing tech solution. It can also be interpreted more broadly, taking the needs of marginalised groups as the starting point and designing tech solutions accordingly. The second interpretation is more in line with CommuniCity's working title 'Innovative Solutions Responding to the Needs of Cities & Communities'. In developing the process, we have given space to both interpretations. The process described in chapter 5 can be applied to existing solutions that need to be adapted and to newly developed tech solutions that are designed from the needs of a marginalised group.

Research

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The experiences gained in the pilots and the research conducted by interviewing (experience) experts, organising or joining meetings and workshops have guided the development of the process described in Chapter 5. Stories from experienced experts from the target group itself and social organisations about tech and their collaboration with governments and tech companies added a lot to our insights.

These insights were also used in describing the context of the process associated with this deliverable. This context describes the position of marginalised groups and their challenges, the function of technology as a contributor to the solution of social challenges and identifies the main bottlenecks in the process of impact creation and co-creation. To give more depth to this context, we have drawn from (scientific) articles on these topics.

Incremental improvement

The deliverable mandates the design of an incremental improvement process. That is, the learning points from upcoming rounds of open calls and pilots within CommuniCity can further feed into the improvement of this deliverable. We have taken a broader view of this incremental task. Even after CommuniCity, better tips, tools and methods should be developed to help improve the process. It will also be interesting to see if the remaining bottlenecks can be tackled further. We want to continue to improve this deliverable by:

- adding learnings from the second and third rounds of open calls and piloting, using them to further refine this deliverable and the process.
- developing workshops to increase understanding of the impact and co-creation criteria, and to improve collaboration with marginalised groups.
- developing an accessible and further expandable toolbox that helps all stakeholders to develop tech solutions that truly contributes to social challenges of marginalised groups, addresses their needs and is understandable and usable.
- recommending follow-up studies and projects that have the potential to contribute to technology development for the challenges faced by marginalised groups. These can no longer be taken up within CommuniCity, but may find a place in future programmes.

Reading guide

Chapter 1 explains the research methodology that led to the identification of the main bottlenecks. Explanation of different marginalised groups and the challenges they face in their lives can be found in Chapter 2. In this chapter, we elaborate on the constraints of time and money within a pilot environment. It also elaborates on the four main bottlenecks in the development of tech solutions for the challenges of marginalised groups. Chapter 3 shows how current technological developments in society cause marginalised groups to become even more remote than they already are and how tech can contribute to improving their position. The importance of impact and co-creation is discussed in Chapter 4. This chapter also elaborates on the importance of empathy and a deep understanding of the position of the target group and the challenge. Chapter 5 describes the incremental process in six phases, from the identification of challenges to the adoption of solutions. It uses the Design Thinking methodology. It also explains how incremental improvement is achieved. The bottlenecks we could not solve within the pilot environment of CommuniCity we have recorded as issues in chapter 6. There we suggest further research and contribute ideas to work towards a solution.

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The practical component of this deliverable is the process in Chapter 5. With this, organisations that want to run pilots or develop tech for marginalised groups can get started. Section 5.2 and Chapter 6 contains suggestions for improvements in various ways, which are indicated by the following icons:

ideas that can still be taken up within CommuniCity

ideas for new projects to discuss within CommuniCity

advice for research and knowledge sharing and any future projects outside CommuniCity.

Note that this deliverable is based on experience and research in European societies, where technology as a solution to societal challenges is more common than in societies where the challenges are more fundamental, such as general poverty, low income, poor health care and education and an even larger gap between rich and poor than in western societies. Even within the participating European cities, a great difference can already be seen in target groups and funding opportunities. The experiences chronicled in this deliverable mainly apply to countries where a social facilities network with temporary funding is available.

For reflection

This deliverable describes a process with methods, tips and tools that can be used when developing tech solutions to the challenges faced by marginalised groups. More important than the methods, tips and tools are the people involved and the challenges they face in life. These challenges cannot simply be solved with a tool or tech. However, tech can help to improve their position. The needs of the target group for which the solution is being developed are central. They are the end users and their needs are at the heart of the design. Without real interest and depth in their situation and the issues in their lives, methods, tips and tools are worth nothing.

1. Research method

To design *A process for incremental improvement and matching the needs of citizens to solutions of tech providers*, we had to learn to understand current experiences from the perspectives of key stakeholders. These are the government (municipality), civil society organisations, tech companies and citizens. We started by finding out what the main bottlenecks are in the current cooperation between these parties when it comes to developing tech solutions. We also sought ideas for solutions to these bottlenecks. As we progressed further in our research, we started to delve into the position of marginalised groups, their challenges and the role of tech in their lives. Following the pilots and the experiences of Helsinki, Porto and Amsterdam, we built a process of incremental learning in which Impact and co-creation have an important place.

1.1 Applied methods

For the purpose of preparing the first open call and for collecting material for this deliverable, we wanted to build on experience of and collect input from a wide range of people. We were interested in the views of people who had already worked on developing technology for marginalised people, views of people who worked with marginalised people but might have no or little experience developing technology for their target groups and people of the target groups themselves who could tell us about their experience with tech. We also thought it was important to collect experiences and views both from people within municipalities as well as from people outside municipalities, both commercial and non-commercial parties.

We obtained the views and experiences of these people in two ways: by one-on-one interviews and by organising or joining meetings and workshops in which participants exchanged ideas and experiences both with each other and with us.

Besides drawing on interviews, meetings and workshops in which people shared and discussed their views, experiences, bottlenecks and suggestions for solutions, for this deliverable we also draw on observations gathered during CommuniCity project meetings and the pilots.

The **interviews** were conducted with different stakeholders and people working in different roles:

- 3 people working for the municipality of Amsterdam with experience in Open Calls
- 4 people working for the municipality of Amsterdam with experience in developing tech for vulnerable groups of citizens
- 3 tech companies with experience in developing tech for vulnerable groups
- 2 social designers
- 3 people of associations working with marginalised communities who have experience with tech projects or are considering using more tech in their work
- 1 person working at the health department of a municipality who has been working on a database for health apps
- 3 people from Porto and Helsinki, with experience in either organizing tech open calls and/or running tech pilots
- 1 person of a matchmaking platform for organizations looking for AI solutions and AI students who are thinking of founding a start-up
- 1 person of a matchmaking platform for non-profit organizations looking for tech solutions and tech companies

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- 1 professor specialised in technology in social work

Later in this chapter, the main learnings from these interviews are summarised, together with the main learnings from the meetings and workshops. The meetings and workshops in which people shared ideas and experiences with each other vary substantially in their design and participants. Therefore, a brief description of each of them is given in the table below.

1.1.1 Timeline of the research

Date and place	Participants	Description
March 23, 2023, Amsterdam, Houthavens	16 participants. Mixture of tech companies, local governments, scholars, associations	Workshop organised by innovation platform Amsterdam Smart City Topic: Bottlenecks and solutions when developing tech for and with marginalised groups
April 17, 2023, Amsterdam, Oud-West	2 social designers 2 people of tech companies 1 person of a tech ngo 3 people of associations working with marginalised groups 2 people of the municipality of Amsterdam 1 teacher of tech design at AUAS	Meeting organised by the municipality of Amsterdam, CommuniCity project Topic: How can associations and tech providers collaborate better on tech solutions for marginalised groups? What are bottlenecks in designing tech for marginalised groups and what are possible remedies?
May 25, 2023, Amsterdam Zuid	20 consultants, 10 companies (commercial businesses and government), 10 different challenges.	'Fixer' event organised by consultancy company 'Innovation Boosters'. Incubator for addressing challenges en look for solutions. Topic Municipality of Amsterdam: How to make tech solutions for marginalised groups scalable?
May 31, 2023, Braga (Portugal)	About 15 people working in the social field in different EU cities	Co Creation workshop organised by the EuroCities Social Innovation Lab Topic: How to (sustainably) fund tech solutions for marginalised groups?
July 3, 2023, Amsterdam Zuidoost	Delegations of each pilot, consisting of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person of the target group - 1 person of the tech company - 1 person of the association - 1 person of the pilot host (municipality) 	Dinner and workshop organised by the municipality of Amsterdam, CommuniCity project Topic: share lessons learned during the pilot, to improve the next round of Open call/pilots. Particularly on cocreation.
Sep 18, 2023, Amsterdam Nieuw-West	Delegations of each pilot, generally consisting of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person of the target group - 1 person of the tech company - 1 person of the association - 1 person of the pilot host (municipality) 	Dinner and workshop organised by the municipality of Amsterdam, CommuniCity project Topic: share lessons learned during the pilot, to improve the next round of Open call/pilots. Particularly on cocreation.

As mentioned in the beginning of this chapter, learnings were also collected by observing the running of the first open call, the first pilots² and the CommuniCity project itself. These observations mainly came about during the following events and activities:

- Communications, actions and results
- Evaluating the proposals received in the first Open call
- WP3/5 meetings
- Consortium meeting June 2023

For describing the context to the process in this deliverable about marginalised groups, social challenges, tech as a solution, impact and co-creation, we have also drawn on (scientific) articles on these topics. These articles can be found in the footnotes and bibliography.

² [CommuniCity Pilots](#)

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1.2 Short recap of the findings

The interviews and sessions with people with different backgrounds provided us with many insights. Articles on social innovation also gave us insights into the main bottlenecks. Below we list the findings that, in different wordings, recurred several times. We have categorised them into what seem to be the most important issues. Below we have grouped some key recurring quotes by bottleneck.

awareness of the value of tech for social challenges

adequately tailored solutions to the needs of marginalized groups

solutions for implementation and maintenance of tech

finance opportunities to develop tech for marginalized target groups

Tech is not perceived as a way of helping our target group.

😊 Tech developers generally have little knowledge of social issues.

😊 If we use tech for social issues, I will soon be out of a job.

😊 Tech is designed for the masses.

😊 Many products are offered without any research into the actual needs of the target group.

😊 We tech developers tend to first create a solution, and then look for a problem.

😊 Tech solutions are developed from a technical perspective and are too complicated for end users.

😊 Which marginalised groups are there and what do they have to deal with?

😊 Use co-creation methods that match with the target group.

😊 Give the target group a voice in the evaluation of the proposals.

😊 Many CSO's do not have the right expertise for implementation and maintenance.

😊 We depend on grants and contracts, there is no budget to hire someone to do this.

😊 Using tech and changing my way of working would demand a large investment in time.

😊 How do I monitor the security and privacy data of my clients?

😊 Often there is no business case, making the technical solution unprofitable.

😊 CSOs depend on temporary grants and contracts, so developing tech is difficult.

😊 Not every target group that needs the tech solution is in the financial position to pay for it.

😊 Marginalised groups are relatively small and the tech solution is difficult to scale up.

1.3 The main bottlenecks

We have described these main issues below as the main bottlenecks. These are the leading bottlenecks that will be addressed in the deliverable. The second bottleneck is the most important one. It ties in with the remit of the deliverable.

1. Tech is generally not yet sufficiently seen as a solution to social challenges of marginalised groups.

Since tech is usually developed for commercial purposes, awareness that tech can contribute to solving societal challenges has not yet sufficiently penetrated. This is true for civil society organisations, governments, tech companies and the marginalised groups themselves. In healthcare, the use of tech (e-health) is the most developed and accepted. Deployment of tech in social challenges such as poverty, unemployment or integration is less developed. This means that much knowledge and expertise can still be built and exchanged to further explore the potential of tech in this area.

2. Due to lack of knowledge of marginalised groups and the challenges they face, tech solutions are often not adequately tailored to their needs.

The social engagement of tech companies is growing. There are more and more tech companies keen to contribute to society in a social way. Yet tech solutions are still too rarely developed in co-creation with the target group. This means too little time is still spent on getting to know the target group in an equal manner. The knowledge of their social position, the challenges involved and their ability to use and understand tech is insufficient. The target group in question is not sufficiently involved as a result, which means that the solution does not sufficiently meet their needs and is not or hardly used.

3. Unfamiliarity with tech often makes it difficult for civil society organisations (CSOs) to implement and maintain developed tools.

Deploying tech for challenges of the target groups CSOs work with is not yet common practice. Partly this has to do with the aforementioned awareness. Partly to the lack of technical expertise, time and money. These are factors that all influence each other. The lack of knowledge and expertise makes it difficult to work with tech. This involves issues of security and reliability of partners and tools developed. Lack of sustainable funding means they cannot put enough capacity on it and expertise to sustainably maintain the application.

4. Having a technical solution developed is often too expensive for marginalised target groups and civil society organisations.

Marginalised groups are generally a small market. As a result, there is often no business case for technology solutions designed for marginalised groups. CSOs often depend on funds and grants for their survival. Because the nature of their social activities prevents them from making a profit, it is difficult for them to save money and make investments. Due to their marginalised position, users often do not have enough money to buy the tools and or take out subscriptions.

In the description of the process in Chapter 5, we will pay particular attention to the second bottleneck. The process described offers tips and tools to better define the target group and the challenges, improve cooperation between tech parties, CSOs, governments and marginalised target groups and create more impact. The remaining three bottlenecks are beyond the scope of our deliverable but are closely related to the success or failure of the pilots and the development of tech solutions for marginalised target groups. We will, however, make suggestions on awareness, implementation and maintenance and funding for follow-up steps in Chapter 6.

1. Challenges of marginalised groups

Marginalised groups face different challenges in everyday life. Their condition of marginality is generally inherited, which makes their condition in society cyclical. These may include physical challenges such as limited or no sight or hearing, or physical disabilities that limit their opportunities in social life. Mental challenges can also limit people in their participation in society. A (mild) intellectual disability, illiteracy or mental health problems can cause considerable (social) disadvantages. And then there are also social situations that can prevent you from keeping up, such as poverty, lack of education, unemployment, a problematic home situation, a position as an immigrant or refugee and loneliness.

There are many more examples of people in marginalised positions. What many of these target groups have in common when looking at their relationship to tech is that they have less easy access to tech than people who have had sufficient opportunities in life. This puts them at a disadvantage that is difficult to catch up with and further isolates them from society. The development of (commercial) tech still pays too little attention to people with disabilities or at a disadvantage. Also tech is still not adequately deployed as a means to solve social problems. **In a society where we are becoming increasingly dependent on tech, this not only puts them at a technological disadvantage but also at a social and societal disadvantage.** For instance, people in poverty cannot access devices that allow them to explore and use these technologies, people with intellectual disabilities and the elderly find it difficult to manage their own bank matters, refugees cannot understand the language on websites and deaf-born people cannot follow the spoken and written news.

2.1 Marginalised groups and tech

A number of marginalised target groups have already been mentioned above. During the interviews, meetings, pilots and evaluations we conducted within CommuniCity, we arrived at a classification of three target groups. This classification helps us understand the position of marginalised target groups vis-à-vis tech and how we can use tech to improve the position of these target groups. These are:

- Physically and mentally challenged.
- Defined by societal challenges.
- Unfamiliar and unaccustomed to tech.

This classification is not arbitrary. One can think of various situations in which people can be categorised under several of the above target groups. For example, a physical disability can lead to a disadvantage in social position, unemployment and poverty and thus little or no access to tech. When it comes to using tech as a tool to improve the position of these target groups, this classification can help to better understand:

- What the marginalised position of these target groups is.
- To what extent tech is already being used for certain marginalised target groups.
- What (social) challenges are involved.
- Which (existing) technology can help solve these challenges.

The social challenges faced by the different target groups also differ. The combination of the social position of the target group, the complexity of the challenge they face and the possibilities of using tech to contribute to solving their challenges also lead to a first step in defining a scope that fits within CommuniCity's pilot environment. The pilot environment itself has limitations in time and money. The more complex a challenge the more time and empathy is needed to really understand what is involved before working on a tech

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solution. Time and money are not always sufficient in a pilot environment. Defining a scope helps make pilots more manageable, feasible and tangible in the future.

One target group is still worth mentioning. These are citizens who do not have sufficient financial resources to purchase tech devices. They are in a disadvantaged position in relation to tech because they have no access to it due to economic incapacity. Often this group has the necessary skills to take full advantage of the technological solution. What is needed for them is not a technological solution but a solution that provides access to tech. In practical terms, this means creating awareness through government, welfare organisations or (large) tech companies that a technological disadvantage can be solved through spreading devices. This can be done, for instance, through social return assignments to large companies, giveaway shops or circular economy networks in neighbourhoods. In pilot situations, this means making devices available for these target groups.

2.1.1 Physically and mentally challenged

The lives of people with physical and/or mental challenges can be improved by technical and digital applications that help them participate in everyday life. Physically, because they cannot hear or see. They are limited in their abilities because they cannot stand or walk, or because they have movement disorders. Mentally because they have intellectual or mental disabilities that make understanding and using technology challenging. In the field of physical and mental care, technology is most advanced. In healthcare, e-health has been used for some time for solutions that ease the task of caregivers. With the use of apps and smart watches, for example, heart rate, saturation and blood pressure can be measured and fall detection can be enabled. There are cuddle robots in care homes to reduce loneliness. Domotics are used for mobility monitoring of the elderly, people with dementia and intellectual disabilities. Technological aids for people with physical disabilities have also been around for some time, such as mobility scooters, electric wheelchairs, adapted cars and aids to lift people in and out of bed.

The above are mostly (digital) tools that relieve healthcare workers and (medical) specialists. The demand for the development of technology thus arose from the professionals who saw an urgency in practising their profession more efficiently³. Technology needed by the target group itself, which is not only focused on care, is currently less developed. For example, there are people with mild intellectual disabilities who would like to manage their banking themselves. Also, people who have difficulty reading and writing often have difficulty with the language used on websites and the understandability of the interface of apps.

2.1.2 Defined by societal challenges

Social positions people are in can also determine their relationship with tech. The family you grow up in (education, parents, family income and migration background) influences your early development as a child and affects your entire school, study and further career, living situation and health. This means that we can develop a disadvantage in society from an early age and experience the effects of this in various areas of life. There is often an accumulation of problems⁴. Technology is also increasingly used for social challenges, but

³ [Movisie - what works in social innovation](#)

⁴ [Social Issues - Opportunity inequality is transferred from generation to generation](#)

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not nearly as often as in healthcare. The Red Cross, for instance, has had the Refugee Buddy developed, an app that helps status holders and asylum seekers find their way around the Netherlands. The Regenbooggroep (shelter for addicts and the homeless) has also had a similar app developed for the homeless. The VR game ReAction is a tool that gives rise to a conversation with young people about their own situation and the possibilities of avoiding knife violence.

Social challenges are increasingly coming into focus when it comes to technology. Governments and civil society organisations are more and more realising that tech can contribute to improving the position of marginalised groups. Well-known examples are platforms and apps in the field of neighbourhood help, combating food waste, the sharing economy and buddy projects as a contribution to reducing poverty and loneliness. For more complex challenges with a sensitive underlayer, there are fewer technological solutions to be found. Topics such as (sexual) abuse, exploitation and discrimination are more difficult to fathom because of their sensitivity. Developing technology to meet these challenges requires a deep understanding of the subject and a secure and confidential relationship with the target group. Partly because of the multi-problem environment, social challenges are harder to grasp than physical and mental challenges.

In several pilots in Amsterdam, we found that the challenge was more complex than expected. Complex challenges such as issues around online abuse or youth crime attracted fewer or no proposals. The proposals that were submitted were based on existing technical solutions that could be adapted to the target group and the challenge. In the end the proposals did not match the needs of the target group as well as initially assumed. Experience also showed that the clearer and simpler a challenge, the easier it was to work towards a solution. There is a limit to the complexity of a challenge that can be submitted in an open call.

Helsinki has formulated several challenges with a set of civil society organisations as cooperation partners. With the Rehabilitative Work Activities department, they have formulated several challenges in the first and second open call that tie in with integration and unemployment. The sustainable cooperation and common threads in these challenges can ensure better and lasting solutions.

From the interviews and workshops we held and the experiences with pilots within CommuniCity, it appears that the target group concerned is often still insufficiently involved in the development of tech applications and there is also little or no testing during the development of the tool in practice. Consequently, solutions regularly do not sufficiently match the needs of the target group for whom the tech application is intended. This makes it difficult to adopt and disseminate the tool developed, and many well-intentioned solutions die a slow death. Just recently, the Dutch Buddy app that was supposed to give people in debt insight into their money matters, loans, repayments and debts was declared bankrupt. Users were reluctant to share personal data, the many notifications in the app caused extra stress and the app's analyses of financial data were incorrect⁵.

Compared to the physically and mentally challenged, the challenges facing this target group are less clear. Which technological solutions really answer their challenges is therefore also less easy to identify. This too

⁵ [Pointer – Financial buddy app bankrupt](#)

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makes the adoption and dissemination of the technological solution more difficult. If people don't really know what they will gain from it, they are not likely to use it.

2.1.3 Unfamiliar with and unaccustomed to tech

There is also a target group that is not used to using tech. Often, people in this target group have not grown up with tech or they come from a country where technology is controlled by the government or a (military) regime. Tech is not seen by them as a tool that can make life a lot easier. There is much discomfort and embarrassment because they do not (fully) understand how it works and the consequences of using it. This is especially the case with digital technology. They cannot oversee the consequences of filling in a web form, for example. This causes distrust. From their point of view, your benefits may just be stopped or your children placed out of home. Distrust in government translates into distrust in systems that require the exchange of untraceable data. At Cybersoek in Amsterdam, a real-life avatar was used to help participants fill in a web form. They did not trust the avatar and felt cheated because it turned out not to be a real person after all.

Working with this vulnerable target group in a pilot situation with limited time is usually difficult. It takes a lot of time and effort to gain their trust and get them used to tech. This requires a different approach from the co-creation methods used to research their needs, define the issue and test prototypes. Ignoring their position and the shame and distrust they feel towards technology can lead to disappointment and further damage to trust. In a pilot situation where limited time and financial resources are available, it is not feasible for this target group to work towards a tech solution and do justice to their needs.

2.1.4 The role of money

In gathering information for our research, we often found that funding and purchase of technology solutions was one of the biggest bottlenecks to accessibility technology for marginalised groups. For many of the above target groups, money is an issue. The majority of technological applications are developed for the commercial market and have a revenue model. To purchase, implement and sustainably maintain technological applications, structural funding is needed. This is chronically lacking among civil society organisations that depend on temporary subsidies and funds and among consumers on low salaries or in a benefit situation. When it comes to technological applications for (medical) care purposes, health insurance schemes and social government programmes are jumping in to provide sustainable solutions. E-health has commercial value and is also used and bought by people who are not under medical treatment but want to stay healthy and fit. Temporary subsidies and funds for social challenges such as poverty or unemployment are made available within established municipal-, state- and European programmes. However, the temporary nature of these instruments and the lack of integrated coordination and knowledge exchange mean that they are still experimental and not sustainable. This also varies greatly from country to country. Funding is an issue at every phase of the process from the challenge to implementation and dissemination of the tech solution and thus affects the possibilities of developing a good and sustainable product and ensuring widespread access to devices. We will look at this in more detail later in this deliverable (chapter 6).

2.1.5 First steps in defining a scope

The constraints of time and money on the ability to address complex challenges in a pilot environment were mentioned earlier in this deliverable. The interviews, workshops, pilots and conversations with colleagues

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within CommuniCity do show that there is a limit to what we can ask of marginalised groups and to the complexity and sensitivity of the challenge. The more complex and sensitive the issue, the more the tech party needs to invest time and immerse themselves in the target group and the challenge. If a challenge is complex, specific co-creation methods will be required to gain the trust of the target group and to sufficiently specify and define the challenge. We will elaborate more on this in the chapter on co-creation (chapter 4).

In Porto, the problem of time and money has been partly addressed by defining a focus area (neighbourhood) and a target group (residents of this neighbourhood) for all projects selected in the CommuniCity Open Calls for Porto. This allows for stronger partnerships to support this community for three years (three open calls). In this way the period of co-creation is extended. Although the target groups were not exactly the same in all solutions, the strategy enables deeper engagement with the target audience. In all open calls, one local association is the challenge owner and therefore the partner that creates the common thread between the different challenges and solutions. this approach has clear benefits and is in line with CommuniCity's objectives, however it falls short of ensuring productive co-creation processes for developing technical solutions.

Although the challenges of the first target group (physically and mentally challenged) tend to be simpler than those of the second (defined by societal challenges), we advocate paying attention to the second target group as well. As mentioned above, e-health has ensured that the technology is already well developed in the area of physical and mental challenges. Through government and health insurance, this technology is also becoming more accessible. Tech for social challenges is lagging behind, and it is precisely projects where experimentation and learning take place that provide an opportunity to learn and disseminate this knowledge. To avoid making a challenge too complicated, it is advisable to define it well. Section 5.1.2 provides (co-creation) methods for this. Before launching this challenge in an open call, a social designer and tech expert can advise on the feasibility of the challenge within the available time and budget.

In conclusion

There are 2 ways to better prepare the scope of a challenge for a next open call and pilot environment:

The challenges can be better formulated and thought out. In Chapter 5, we will provide methods for this at sections 5.1.1. Detecting challenges and 5.1.2 Articulating the needs. Involve a social designer and a tech expert to advise on the feasibility of the challenge. Involve an experience expert in the evaluation of proposals, who can check whether the proposer has a good understanding of the challenge and the target group. We will elaborate on this further in section 5.1.3.5 Co-creation methods to involve the target group

3 Tech as a solution to social challenges

Technology has become an indispensable part of our daily lives. Everything we do, from the beginning to the end of the day, involves some form of technology. Technological innovation allows us to communicate with each other faster, place online orders, set our heating remotely, have robot hoovers do our work, secure our home and track our health digitally. These are all innovations designed to make our lives more efficient and easier. Often, these technological applications are tailored to the needs of the educated majority who are well placed in society.

For people who have not grown up with (digital) technology, have difficulties with reading, do not trust technology, do not understand it or cannot afford it, it is becoming increasingly difficult to get along in everyday life. They have little or no access to necessary information and equipment needed to handle important matters, such as banking, finding work, applying for benefits or passports. Opportunities in the labour market are also getting slimmer as digital skills are increasingly important while performing work. Social media are becoming increasingly important for your social network and participation in social activities. Thus, the risk of social exclusion is increasing and inequality between people with and without digital and technological skills is growing.

How can we ensure that the gap does not keep widening, make tech accessible to marginalised groups and develop more tech for challenges they face in their daily lives?

How can technological innovation lead to social innovation, inclusion and equality?

This deliverable already provides several examples of how tech can improve the lives of marginalised groups. Tech can improve the position of marginalised groups physically and socially. Recently, a small and handy device has been developed that allows blind users to type Braille easily and quickly on smartphones. There are simple educational programmes that teach people how to use computers and smartphones. AI simplifies complicated texts so that low-literate people can also understand them and robots can support people with intellectual disabilities in raising their children. In this way, various target groups can better keep up in society. Technology can provide them with a social network, more independence to manage their own lives, access to opportunities they did not have before (health, work) and keep them up to date with essential information. This leads to greater inclusion and equality⁶.

The above question is not only answered by examples of tech solutions to social issues. Besides the solution itself, achieving inclusivity and equality is also about how these solutions are developed. During our research into a working process, the term inclusive design came up regularly. By inclusive, this meant not only involving the target group itself in the design of the solution. It also called for a social standard where it is common for tech innovation to take into account as much diversity as possible, so that as many people as possible are able to benefit from tech innovation and new solutions do not have to be arranged for separate target groups afterwards. For example, a banking app could be developed together with people with mild intellectual disabilities and people who have difficulty reading. The 'mainstream target group' also understands such a design so that the app is usable for multiple people. Unfortunately, this is not yet

⁶ [Pharos - Vulnerable groups in research and practice](#)

sufficiently well established and it often appears that various groups cannot keep up with technological developments which further increases their existing disadvantage in society.⁷

3.1 Awareness of tech opportunities

Paragraph 2.2 describes the main bottlenecks. The first bottleneck is about the awareness that tech can contribute to solving societal challenges. This has not yet sufficiently penetrated with governments, tech companies and social organisations.

1. Tech is generally not yet sufficiently seen as a solution to social challenges of marginalised groups.

When it comes to societal challenges, a difference in awareness can be seen in solutions in physical and mental health in which e-health is developing rapidly, or social challenges such as unemployment or loneliness. When it comes to technology, society still pays little attention to the latter issues.

Chapter 2 has already described that there are several marginalised groups facing different social challenges. For example, people who find it difficult or impossible to read or write, or do not speak the language of the country, various tech solutions are already being deployed such as the read-aloud functions on websites, the ability to enlarge text, record or translate it. There are also emerging tools that simplify existing text or convert text into a video with avatar. These are existing solutions that are constantly being developed and becoming more sophisticated with the help of AI. Often, these are adaptations of existing technology that are thereby made more inclusive. Awareness of the potential of these tech solutions as a contribution to solving social challenges is growing. The technology has already proven itself and is becoming easier to apply.

In healthcare, e-health has taken off. This technology is used for people who need physical, medical and mental care. Some examples have already been mentioned in Chapter 2. This field continues to innovate and is increasingly used to give people insight into their own health, to be more aware of it and to keep more control. In Amsterdam, for instance, a digital front door is being developed to better refer residents to the right care. Another example is the SAM app (Stress Autism Mate) launched a year ago, which provides insight into sensitivity to stimuli for people with autism. In the above examples, awareness of the potential to apply technology for social purposes is high, and knowledge exchange, collaboration and research are taking place to improve existing technologies, apply them to new challenges and develop new technology.

Helsinki formulated challenges in the field of e-health for people with disabilities, pressure ulcers and homecare clients in the first and second round of open calls. For the further development of this deliverable and to learn from the second and third round pilots, it is interesting to compare the outcomes of these pilots with the challenges that address social issues. These examples can help improve the identification and formulation of challenges within programmes such as CommuniCity.

⁷ [Yasmin Yusuf - Why accessibility in design should never be an afterthought](#)

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Funding opportunities for this technology are also ample. Health, self-reliance and prevention are high on the agenda. Some of this technology is commercial and profitable. When it comes to prevention, reducing costs in healthcare and effective deployment of staff, health insurers and governments are happy to assist in the development of tech solutions. The demand for this technology arose from healthcare providers. From the urgency to make care cheaper and more efficient and to relieve care workers.

It is a different story with challenges dealing with the social position of marginalised target groups. In this area, awareness is still low.

In Amsterdam, challenges were identified by introducing CommuniCity to colleagues in the municipality who work with civil society organisations, social issues and technology development. Civil society organisations were then approached to explore the challenges and the possibility of developing a technical solution for them. It was difficult for these organisations, who were not used to thinking in terms of technological solutions, to come up with a suitable challenge to nominate. Most of the challenges came from the municipality.

There are several reasons for this. There is little or no money to be made from developing apps and tools against poverty, unemployment, discrimination, homelessness or crime prevention. The challenges are complex and sensitive. Target groups that are digitally disadvantaged find it difficult to pay for the purchase. Section 2.1 under main bottlenecks shows that the civil society organisations that support them have little to no expertise and financial resources to develop, implement and maintain tech. Tech as a solution to these societal challenges is therefore hardly on their radar, if at all. Also for tech parties, developing tech solutions for these target groups is not financially attractive. However, there are tech parties that are socially aware and want to contribute to society. Nevertheless, the focus on these kinds of challenges is still quite low. Tech parties still have little knowledge of the disadvantaged position of these target groups and the challenges they face in everyday life. There is still a world to be won and it is worth finding out what the preventive effect of using tech for these challenges is, how we can improve the position of these target groups and what this means for society as a whole.

3.2 Tech as a value to society

Developing technological solutions to societal challenges requires not only money but also social awareness. That (large) tech companies can add value to society with their expertise is well known. The examples that can be found are mainly about tech solutions for sustainability, circular economy, (medical) health issues, (international) security, education or solutions to, for instance, the refugee crisis or flood prevention. Besides the social impact that companies like to contribute to, these are also topics that are under the spotlight (internationally). Because these challenges receive a lot of attention, investments are also made in tech innovations. If there is "political will" access to technology can become much more equitable and universal. Funding will then be made available and additional effort is made by the government to ensure equitable access to technology, particularly in the educational context. With this attention, more tech companies will also invest in support, training and donation of digital resources to target groups with a digital disadvantage to ensure they can connect to the existing digital society (digital inclusion).

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This is part of the solution but it does not yet deliver sufficient impact for the social problems of people in deprivation. As a result, people in poverty are not yet out of debt, the long-term unemployed do not yet have a job, children are still bullied and the homeless do not have a roof over their heads. Being able to participate fully in the society you live in is not a given for everyone. These issues have their roots in society itself, the way social safety nets are regulated and whether there is a culture of inclusion or exclusion. The awareness that tech companies can be impactful like large supermarket chains support local football clubs and those football clubs launch campaigns against discrimination has not yet sunk in sufficiently. From the idea that we are all part of a society and can influence it with our expertise, network and resources, we can also take responsibility to contribute to the solution of these challenges and thus contribute to social inclusion, justice and equality.

A culture of social inclusion can take shape in how we view tech development and whether we need to make a profit or contribute to social impact. Are we making a business case or a value case? The two need not be mutually exclusive. Developing technology is often not cheap, revenue needs to be generated and room for investment is needed. But the idea of a value case is not foreign. Thinking that we don't just have to make a profit, but can also make a social contribution, is going to open up new perspectives. The development of tech will likely become more inclusive and may be better distributed to people who need it but cannot afford it. A successful and practical example is Tech To The Rescue⁸. This platform has a permanent matching service with which they contribute to the Tech for Good movement by linking tech companies that want to create social impact with non-profit organisations with a social challenge. They provide pro bono tech services for this purpose. Additionally, they organise hackathons on international refugee crisis and environmental issues. In chapter 6, we will elaborate on the concept of a value case.

In conclusion

To raise awareness, it is important to generate more attention to the challenges of marginalised groups. By exchanging knowledge, ideas and opportunities between civil society organisations, governments, tech companies and these target groups, there will be growing expertise and more mutual understanding. This way, we can work on solutions that matter and are valuable not only for the target groups themselves but for society as a whole. In section 6.1 we will elaborate on this.

⁸ <https://www.techtotherescue.org/>

4 Impact and co-creation

Within CommuniCity, impact and co-creation are very important. Developing tech for marginalised groups requires a different approach and method than developing tech for the commercial market. It is important to understand what the target group's situation is and whether what is being developed has real impact for the target group and the challenge they are dealing with. It still happens regularly that solutions are devised for social challenges in which the target group itself has little or no involvement. Co-creation ensures that there is a better understanding between the target group and the tech party, the issue becomes more understandable, the advice and ideas of the target group are included in the design and real solutions are developed that fit their situation and needs. **Co-creating can be done in many different ways.** This chapter pays special attention to creating impact for and co-creation with marginalised groups.

4.1 Impact and social value

Involving end users in the development of a tech solution is essential for the end result. Marginalised target groups are less likely to be involved in co-creation than 'regular' target groups. They move around in other social networks, or they have very little connection to them. As a result, it takes more time to gain trust and understand the complex issues they are facing. Nevertheless, it pays to look for ways to involve them. Only they can make clear what it means to be poor, unemployed or mentally challenged.

Creating technological solutions to societal challenges has impact on the lives of several marginalised groups in various ways:

1. **Individual impact of the co-creation process on self-determination and empowerment:** Involving the target group gives them a serious role in the development of the technical solution. It allows them to contribute knowledge, expertise and ideas. This builds self-confidence and self-esteem and has an emancipatory effect.
2. **Social impact of tech solutions in the networks of the target groups:** Tech solutions can also have social impact. There are several known solutions that connect people and build social networks in the neighbourhood. In this way, tech can also improve people's social lives. For example, a neighbourhood help app can reduce feelings of loneliness and improve social networking in the neighbourhood, increasing safety.
3. **Societal impact of tech by creating solutions to social challenges:** Technology can also pick up issues that occur regularly in society. If a VR game contributes to reducing knife violence among young people or decreasing bullying behaviour, then tech contributes to solving an overall societal problem.

When assessing the proposals, it is important to also carefully assess the impact on the target audience at these three levels. Several tech companies offered existing tech products in their proposals. In itself, this is quite possible if the solution can be adapted in such a way that the target group benefits. In Porto this resulted in companies applying to the Open Call as an opportunity to get feedback from potential new users/markets. This not with the intention of co-creating with the target audience but for gathering feedback.

4.1.1 The measurability of impact

In the examples above, it becomes clear that impact that contributes to creating social value often has to do with a feeling. Less stress, less loneliness, a different perspective on bullying or a greater sense of safety. Impact of these technologies can be measured quantitatively by measuring the number of users and the frequency with which the tool is used, or the number of unemployed people who got a job thanks to an app or the decrease in reports of discrimination. User and satisfaction experiences in this case are important to include to know whether real impact has been realised. To determine what impact can be achieved with the development of a tech solution, it is important to understand the situation of the target group and look for the value it adds to their lives, their self-esteem and empowerment and to a social problem in society. Co-creation is very important here.

4.2 Co-creating with marginalised groups

Co-creation has many positive benefits. Not only does it contribute to a supported end result and a solution that truly meets the needs of the marginalised target group. It is also sustainable and contributes to the empowerment of the target groups being involved. Listed below are the benefits of good co-creation⁹:

- The **result optimally matches** the wishes and needs of the target group.
- Only **solutions that are truly relevant** to the target group are developed
- There is **a lot of support** because the open nature of the process gives all those involved a feeling that it is really theirs and made by them and for them.
- **Adoption becomes easier** because positive experiences start circulating.
- **Motivation is high** because it is jointly determined for whom the product is made and why.
- Ultimately, this results in a **benefit in costs**. A good co-creation process prevents wrong decisions, unnecessary expenses, wasted time and assumptions that lead to tensions and faulty elaborations.

The above benefits can be disadvantageous if the co-creation process is not set up properly, the wrong (research) methodologies are used or co-creation is only used in certain parts of the process. Good co-creation requires involvement of the target group from start to finish of the whole process, from challenge to adoption, the whole system in the room.

4.2.1 What is co-creation

Co-creation is a form of collaboration in which all participants have an influence on the process and the outcome of that process, such as a plan, advice or product. Co-creation is characterised by dialogue, 'common ground', enthusiasm, decisiveness and a focus on results. Successful co-creation requires equality of participants, reciprocity, openness and trust.

⁹ Order in chaos: 6 benefits of complete co-creation - Stefanie Jansen and Maarten Pieters

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The target group plays an active role throughout the process of co-creation from identifying the issue to adopting the solution. There is a continuous creative process, in which the collaboration between tech company and target group ultimately leads to real value creation. A key premise of co-creation is that neither the tech company nor the target group can arrive at the ideal solution without collaboration. Together, they possess the full knowledge and skills needed to develop a solution that truly matches the issue and needs of the target audience. Co-creation does not stop after one session. It is an iterative process where you can constantly return to previous phases in the process and gather inspiration, ideas or feedback again.

The methods used in co-creation are often creative. The idea is to simulate situations where we break free from our fixed assumptions and actually come up with different ideas. Examples are drawing a future, role playing and using lego. Stimulating creative ability helps people solve difficult social challenges. Working visually, creatively and actively stimulates the imagination and creates energy in the process. It gives you the ability to adapt, live during the session, the activities to the participants' curiosity and imagination. True positive impact of a co-creation session requires creativity and sensitivity to read people, on the part of the moderator. Working together with creative methodologies creates the energy with which you can make an impact and also get people involved that you would otherwise not reach.

Social innovation is also referred to as human-centred design, which uses co-creation methods to develop innovative solutions. The premise of human-centred design is that all problems, even seemingly intractable ones such as poverty, gender inequality and unemployment, are solvable. The assumption is that the people who deal with these problems every day are the ones who hold the key to the answer. Involving them creates the feeling of being part of the solution. It breaks the cycle of dependency and shows that they can do something about their own situation¹⁰.

Co-creation is still confused with consultation and in-depth knowledge of the target group. For example, research methods such as focus groups, (in-depth) interviews and surveys are sometimes added to the co-creation strategy. These are often methods to gain an in-depth understanding of the target group or where people are asked for feedback or advice. These methods are not co-creative, but they can be part of a co-creation process as preparation.

Several proposals Amsterdam received on the challenges included common research methods such as interview, survey and focus groups. These methods were introduced as co-creation. They are good methods to get to know the issue and the target group better, but it does not give the target group an equal say in interpreting the issue. The use of co-creation methods that involve the target group itself in exploring the issue can lead to a different definition of the issue and thus to different solutions. For this reason, Amsterdam started offering workshops on co-creation in the second pilot round.

4.2.2 Co-creation with marginalised groups

Existing methods of engaging residents tend to exclude vulnerable or marginalised groups. Meetings are too far away, inaccessible by public transport or too unsafe because it is an unknown place. In a

¹⁰ Field guide to human-centered design

conversational setting, not everyone is able to express his or her opinion well. Online surveys and interviews are not accessible to everyone. Shame and low self-esteem also play a role. People who live in a disadvantaged position for a long time do not have the luxury to think about what they find important and valuable. They are surviving. Co-creation with marginalised groups requires methods that match their living environment. This means that co-creation must often take place close to the target group and in an interactive form in the community in which they live. Starting with self-guided tours of the habitat, introduction- and trust games will break the ice.

4.3 Understanding the target group

It is already described earlier in this deliverable that tech solutions for marginalised groups are still often developed without them. This also means that the challenges to be solved are viewed from the perspective of the government, a civil society organisation or the developer. The analysis of the challenge then already starts with assumptions that do not fit the target group's situation, leading to solutions that do not meet their needs. In (tech) innovation, it is important to immerse yourself in the target group and involve them throughout the process. They should be constantly at the centre of the entire design process. Human-centred design is based on empathy, on the idea that the people you design for are your roadmap to innovative solutions. Immersing yourself in another world not only opens you up to new creative possibilities, but it also allows you to leave behind preconceived ideas and outdated ways of thinking. Empathising with the people you design for is the best way to truly understand the context and complexity of their lives. In this way, you'll learn how to better understand people. You'll observe their lives, hear their hopes and desires, and get smart on your challenge¹¹.

4.3.1 Understanding the position of marginalised groups

When working with people from marginalised groups, it is important to immerse yourself in their position. Visit the target group in their own environment and invest time in making contact and building trust. Meetings in rooms of official bodies can be too high a threshold. It is often advisable to meet the target group in the neighbourhood and get in touch with them through key figures who enjoy trust. When working together in groups where there are large differences in knowledge and social position, a personal approach can offer more equality, where everyone is equally valued on their own expertise and skills. This includes appropriate rewards for the time and knowledge they put in. Cultural sensitivity is also important to consider. Sex, gender, but also migration status and cultural background can affect how you approach people, for instance, whether you are a man allowed to interview a woman, need an interpreter or whether or not it is common to talk about your personal situation. Investing in trust and awareness of your own culture and assumptions is very important in this collaboration.

4.3.2 Understanding the challenge

Delving into the challenge of marginalised groups offers great insight into the real problem. Sometimes we think we already know what is going on. Studies, publications, news and social media often publish a lot

¹¹ Field guide to human-centered design

about poverty, unemployment, living with an intellectual disability or what it means to be an immigrant. However, no one knows what it is like to live with a disability or in a disadvantaged position. If you don't experience it yourself, you don't know what it is like not being able to enter with your wheelchair, not understanding the letters from the tax office or what it is like to send your child to school without food. Without delving deeper into the real problem, you won't come up with the right ideas and creative solutions either, but you will be stuck with what you already know. That often automatically leads to adapting or optimising existing solutions. This may suit the needs of the target group, but it may also be that real innovation or some other adaptation is needed. It offers many advantages to immerse yourself in the position and challenge of the target group you are designing for early on in the development of a tech solution. It also serves to break generalizations (being an immigrant is not the same for all immigrants) and understand the diversity of each group, since everyone is the intersection from many groups. You get a better understanding and feel for the group itself and their challenge, thus creating better ideas that fit well with their needs.

5 A process of incremental improvement

This chapter concerns a practical process for developing technological solutions to the challenges of marginalised groups. It provides a handle on the second bottleneck described in section 2.2.

2. Due to lack of knowledge of the target group and the challenges they face, tech solutions are often not adequately tailored to their needs.

The process describes the development of a tech solution for marginalised groups in six different phases, from identifying societal challenges to adopting the tech solution. The context provided in previous chapters shows that especially the challenges and the target groups for which the solution is developed are very different from commercial technology development. Developing tech solutions with, by and for marginalised groups requires understanding and empathy. The issues are social, not commercial. It is not always easy to talk about poverty, unemployment, low literacy or discrimination, for example. These are sensitive issues, not easy to address, and it takes courage to be open about one's own difficult situation in a society that tells you that if you are doing well, you are worthwhile. This therefore also requires different methods and approaches aimed at creating a trusting environment and respectful relationship in which the target group's challenge is central, human centred. The process described below provides practical tips and tools for this.

Section 2.2 deals with more recurring bottlenecks that affect the process but were not part of the pilots within CommuniCity. Awareness of tech as a contributor to solving challenges of marginalised groups (bottleneck 1) affects everything. If the urgency to develop tech for challenges of marginalised groups is not seen, social and political attention and funding is lacking. The interest for stakeholders to develop tech for these target groups is then still too small. Projects like CommuniCity do contribute to this awareness. Funding (bottleneck 3) is needed at all phases of the process. Without sufficient and sustainable funding, it is difficult to work on qualitatively sustainable solutions that really meet the needs of the target group. Implementation and maintenance of tech solutions (bottleneck 4) is essential to actually get the tool up and running and keep it functional. In Chapter 6, we will elaborate on these bottlenecks and offer advice and ideas to further explore them and work towards a solution.

The process was partly developed from our experiences within the first round of CommuniCity in which the cities of Helsinki, Porto and Amsterdam ran several pilots. Our interviews with (experiential) experts and several (research) articles also contributed to the development of this process. Within CommuniCity, the participating cities approached the six phases described below in different ways. These variations in approach will be explained in the various phases of the process.

A pilot environment is set up to learn, turn these learning points into advice to then set up better processes in practice. In the CommuniCity pilot, financial resources, personnel capacity and time acted as constraints, which meant that the entire process could not always be completed from start to finish. The process described below assumes an ideal situation where time, money and capacity are sufficiently available.

Co-creation with and impact for the target group for which technology is being developed is an important part of CommuniCity. These two aspects are part of all phases in the process. Therefore, co-creation is seen as a process in which the target group is constantly involved.

5.1 The process

The process in this deliverable is based on human-centred design (design thinking). In technology development, Design Thinking is a common method for getting to the bottom of complex problems, making them manageable and looking for creative solutions that are then continually improved through various phases of testing. Co-creation is an integral part of design thinking. It is a creative and practical way of working that involves the target group from start to finish, from the formulation of the challenge to the adoption of the solution. This way of working has been adopted in the field of social innovation. It is also known as social design or human-centred design. The co-creation methods developed within human-centred design put the target group at the centre of the whole design process. They are designed to create an atmosphere of trust and to get to the heart of vulnerable, sensitive and complex challenges. It is a way of creating equality between different stakeholders.

The different phases of the process are briefly described below. Each phase is then elaborated with an aim, a description, some tips and the (co-creation) methods that can be applied:

1. Detecting challenges:
Finding challenges of marginalised groups for which technology can contribute to the solution.
2. Articulating the needs:
Articulating the challenge according to the needs of the target group.
3. Matching tech partners:
Ways to find suitable tech partners for the development of the technological solution.
4. Development of the tech solution:
The development of the tech solution.
This phase can again be divided into five phases:
Empathise, Define, Ideate, Prototype and Test
5. Implementation and maintenance
To implement a technical solution in a system and to keep it up to date.
6. Adoption:
The commissioning of the tech solution by the target group.

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Figure 1: visualisation of the process.

Each phase is described in the following sections:

1. Aim of the phase
2. Description of the phase
3. Tips
4. (Co-creation) methods and tools

The tips, methods and tools have been collected from literature review, interviews, meetings, workshops and pilots. The tips help to start each phase. They are intended to create preconditions and starting points for the respective phase and to facilitate cooperation with the target group. The methods consist of practical methods (practices) and tools (instruments) to go through the different phases in a co-creative way. They are existing methods and tools from the practice of co-creation, co-design and design thinking, such as canvases and games. For each phase, methods are provided that fit the objective of the phase and are suitable for working with a marginalised group. These different methods come from different toolboxes that can be found online. For each method, reference is made to the toolbox and site where the method is described in detail. A list of toolboxes can be found at the back of this deliverable.

Tips and practical methods for working together and moving forward throughout the process are helpful and make the process tangible. However, it is important to understand the process and the idea behind it. What we have learnt from the CommuniCity pilots is that it is very important to understand the challenge and the position of the marginalised group. There are many co-creation methods in the design thinking toolkits and literature for the prototyping and testing phase. Less attention is paid to methods for defining the challenge with the target group. We are used to understanding their situation through interviews, surveys and focus groups and then starting to prototype. When it comes to social issues, it is important to really define the issue with the target group.

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These methods will only work if we are prepared to put ourselves in the shoes of the end user and put aside our own assumptions. This applies to all product development. Working with marginalised groups can be vulnerable, emotional and complex, but it can also be very interesting, inspiring and rewarding. If we really get to know our target group, put ourselves in their shoes and know how to create a confidential environment, then we can give them ownership and really develop solutions that contribute to their needs. This requires an open and interested attitude and an empathetic approach.

Below is a list of **Good practices** drawn from the experience of prior projects and the pilots of CommuniCity:

- Involve the community for whom the solution is developed from the very beginning and at each phase, including the implementation and evaluation phases.
- If you do not have contact with the community for whom you develop, collaborate with intermediaries, such as associations working with the community.
- In sessions with the community you develop for, first make explicit users' needs before you define concrete requirements for the solution.
- Meet the community where they are located, rather than make them meet you. When organising co-creation sessions, pick venues that are familiar and easy to reach for them.
- Aim to increase the diversity of your team, ideally including people who represent or identify with the community for whom the solution is developed.
- Limit the size of group sessions with users and work at fostering an atmosphere where all are welcomed to speak and listened to (if needed, organise multiple sessions to decrease the size of the group participating).
- Use language/words and visual language that the community can relate to and feels comfortable with.
- Aim to stimulate a sense of ownership amongst participating community members by acknowledging their contribution and incorporating their input.
- Make expectations explicit. In the pilots of CommuniCity make explicit that participants are taking part in a pilot and the developed solution may not be implemented, even if the pilot itself is successful.
- Ask participating community members how they would like to benefit from their participation and ensure it is an exchange where all participants benefit.
- When co-creating with community members, actively work to minimize harm for participants and minimize the risk of feelings of disappointment and exploitation.
- Respect the efforts and time put in by participants by ensuring they will benefit from the exchange.

5.1.1 Detecting challenges

5.1.1.1. Aim

To identify challenges faced by marginalised groups for which technology can contribute to a solution.

5.1.1.2 Description

Because tech as a solution to a challenge faced by marginalised groups is not yet very common, governments, NGOs, technology companies and the target groups themselves will not easily think of tech solutions. Challenges do not appear by themselves and the possibility of finding the solution in tech needs to be encouraged. Finding challenges therefore requires active searching and determining whether the

challenge is suitable for tech solutions. Mostly it is government agencies, civil society organisations or even tech companies that come up with a challenge. How do we know if the target group itself sees it as a challenge and is waiting for a tech solution? Within CommuniCity, there is a strong focus on co-creation. It is important to involve the target group in the challenge. They should also recognise it as such and be involved in articulating the challenge and the development of the solution.

5.1.1.3 Tips

- Involve government departments working on social issues.
- Involve civil society organisations that work with marginalised target groups.
- Reach out to key people in local communities who have contact with the target group.
- Many things have been tried, succeeded and failed. Dig deeper and research why some tech solutions have worked and others have not.
- Involve an experienced tech expert to determine whether tech can contribute to the challenge.

5.1.1.4 Methods to collect challenges

Research into current issues

There are challenges that have been waiting for a technological solution for some time. A current social problem for which there is no money, for which the target group is "too small" to pay attention, or for which commercial organisations see no urgency because it is not profitable. Research among civil society organisations and municipal departments dealing with social issues always reveals a number of urgent challenges. Depending on the financial resources and time available, a technical expert can consider which challenges are most appropriate to address.

Focus on a specific target group

Different target groups have different challenges that tech can help solve. In cooperation with a social organisation that has direct contact with the target group, different challenges that apply to a specific target group can be collected. This can be done through interactive workshops with the social organization and/or the target group. They can then work with a tech expert to identify the most appropriate challenges.

Porto experimented with co-creation in the selection of themes for the second Open Call. In the time available, it failed to engage the target audience, but several local associations that work daily with this population participated. A workshop was held where: first, there was brainstorming about locally faced problems, and then the various problems were grouped into clusters, which help to design the Open Call challenges. To allow for the deepening of themes more time is needed to run multiple sessions and apply different co-creation methods.

Collect recurring challenges

While identifying challenges that qualify for a tech solution, we are collecting challenges. In this way, we are developing a database of challenges waiting for a tech solution. Thus, we can learn what are recurring challenges and where the most demand is. A good example is Tech To The Rescue. As an intermediary between social organisations and tech companies they receive social challenges that require a tech solution. In this way, they build a database of what is needed and what are recurring issues. Collecting

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challenges from civil society organisations can help identify what is going on and where the urgency lies. Building such a database also helps to respond to needs in time and to start working on the right issues.

5.1.1.5 Co-creation methods to involve the target group

The following co-creation methods can be used to engage audiences who cannot read easily, are not used to talking about themselves, or find it difficult to explain what they are struggling with.

Guided tour

Asking some community members to show you around their workplace, home or neighbourhood will give you an insight into their habits and values. This will give you a better idea of the challenges they face than an interview or a conversation on the street¹².

Peers observing Peers

Using key members of the community as researchers helps you retrieve more information than you will manage on your own. Valued members have prestige and trust. Moreover, it can also resolve cultural issues if, for example, a woman is not allowed to be interviewed by a man or if it is about sensitive topics. It is also very empowering for the community if they can do their own research and thus contribute to the solution¹³.

Photojournal

Getting people to take their own photos of their (living) environment is often a good way to start a conversation. It could be about health, food or finances. The photos people take themselves say something about how they see the topic. This method also gives them time to think about the topic themselves before discussing it¹⁴.

Card sort

Card Sort is an easy way to start a conversation about what matters most to your target audience. A stack of cards with words and/or images will evoke different associations for different people. The words and pictures can be tailored to the challenge at hand. By asking them to sort the cards in order of importance, you can gain insight into what is most important to them. This also allows you to initiate a deeper conversation to gain insight into the motivation behind it¹⁵.

¹² [Design Kit - guided tour](#)

¹³ [Design Kit - peers observing peers](#)

¹⁴ [Design Kit - photojournal](#)

¹⁵ [Design Kit - card sort](#)

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5.1.2 Articulating the needs

5.1.2.1. Aim

To refine the challenge according to the needs of the target group.

5.1.2.2 Description

To really understand what a challenge is about it is important to refine the challenge, to find out where the impact should land and what the target audience really needs. This means digging in and empathising with the target group to get the answers you need to create a good challenge. Bear in mind that the challenge should be neither too narrow nor too broad. Too narrow a challenge will not leave enough room for creative solutions. And a broad challenge won't give you any idea where to start.

5.1.2.3 Tips

- Involve the target group themselves in refining the challenge.
- Go to the target group, organise something in their immediate environment.
- Don't make the group too large.
- Use understandable language.
- Prevent professionals from being in the majority.
- Enlist the help of a social designer or social design students.
- Make sure that someone the target group trusts is present (key people or social organisations).
- Use accessible, understandable and visual methods

5.1.2.4 Methods to scope the challenge

The following methods can be used if the challenge is still too broad. These methods can be carried out with the social organisation and/or with a few people from the target group. They are intended as a first step, before delving deeper into the situation of the target group.

Frame your design challenge

The Frame Your Design Challenge worksheet will help you determine the right framework for the challenge. Through a series of steps, it shows the impact and also takes into account the context and constraints of the challenge. A well framed challenge allows for a variety of solutions.¹⁶

Align on your impact goals

This method helps you to think carefully about the impact you want to calculate with the challenge. It allows you to distinguish between long-term and short-term goals. The most immediate impact will generally become the focus of the design¹⁷.

¹⁶ [Design Kit – Frame Your Design Challenge](#)

¹⁷ [Design Kit – Align on your impact goals](#)

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Define your audience

Mapping the ecosystem around your target audience gives you a better sense of the community they live in, the organisations and networks that are important to them and the political system that influences their lives¹⁸.

Design Project Scoping Guide

The guide to project scoping guide offers five elements to frame a challenge. This encourages you to think about the stakeholders, the context the goal and the crux. The templates leave enough room to explore the challenge further and add new information in collaboration with the target group¹⁹.

Articulating the challenge

This method helps to get the challenge clear as participants indicate which issue they think is important to tackle. To get the participants on the same page, their preferences are discussed²⁰.

5.1.2.5 Co-creation methods for understanding the target group

Bodystorming

Bodystorming is a method for researchers and designers to understand what it is like to be in the user's shoes. Bodystorming combines role-playing and simulation and takes place in the target group's environment. This creates empathy for the users. The designers or researchers can observe the users and participate in the bodystorming session²¹.

Empathy timeline

In creating an empathy timeline, participants are creatively engaged in unravelling the challenge. In this way, they become aware of their own experiences and viewpoints. These experiences and views can be used to sharpen the challenge and really understand what the issue is about²².

Collage

Making a collage allows participants to stick images and words on a piece of paper that express personal experiences and feelings. This makes it easier to start a conversation about sensitive topics²³.

Problem Framing

The Problem Framing canvas ensures that everyone can participate equally in defining the challenge and determining the scope. If the canvas is still too difficult to fill in at first, the link to the canvas contains a number of suggestions for first formulating different sub-problems within the challenge and getting an idea of the target groups.²⁴

¹⁸ [Design Kit – Define your audience](#)

¹⁹ [Institute of design at Stanford – Design Project Scoping Guide](#)

²⁰ [University of Twente - Articulating the challenge](#)

²¹ [Think Design - Body Storming](#)

²² [Unalab Enoll – Empathy timeline](#)

²³ [Design Method Toolkit - Collage](#)

²⁴ [Innovation Toolkit - Problem Framing](#)

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5.1.3 Matching tech partners

5.1.3.1 Aim

Find the right tech partners.

5.1.3.2 Description

A common bottleneck heard in the interviews, meetings and workshops we conducted and attended is that it is difficult to find the right tech partners. There are several reasons for this that are already mentioned in this deliverable. It is not yet common enough to develop technology as a contribution to solving social problems. Civil society organisations depend on grants and funds for their survival. Based on our research, it appears that they generally do not have sufficient capacity and financial resources to develop tech solutions. For that reason they are not used to working with tech partners on tech solutions. So how do you know how to find the right partner? Good preparation, as described in the first two phases of this process, is important. When the challenge is clear and we know that tech can contribute to the solution, it is easier to find the right partners.

5.1.3.3 Tips

- Ensure that the challenge is clear.
- Involve civil society organisations and members of the marginalised group in finding the right partner.
- If necessary, involve a social designer or social design students who can make the translation between challenge and tech.
- Make sure your key points for finding the right partner are clear, articulate them in your call for proposals and assess your partner on this basis (see list of key points in 5.1).
- Involve a technical expert who can assess whether potential partners are sufficiently technically underpinned.
- Involve a co-creation expert who can assess whether co-creation methods are appropriate for working with marginalised groups.

5.1.3.4 Methods to find the right partners

The following advice and ideas are described separately, but can also be combined.

Involving Social Designers

Social designers are trained to approach complex (social) issues in a creative way. They work on projects like loneliness, neighbourhood deprivation and debt problems, but also in healthcare and business. They are used to working with marginalised groups and to putting them at the centre of the development of ideas and the final design. This means using user-centred design principles to listen, learn, understand and innovate beyond commerce. They can make the connection between the challenge and tech and help find the right tech partner.

Open call

In an open call, the challenge is posted online and given as much publicity as possible through the media channels from which technology companies get their information. Tech companies can submit proposals that offer a solution to the challenge. As well as a clear challenge, an open call will also have criteria that tech companies must meet when submitting a proposal. These criteria can describe important principles of

co-creation and impact, and set conditions on the technical requirements and quality of the proposal. If a civil society organisation or government issues the open call, it is again important to involve the target group itself in the evaluation of the proposals. Experts in technology and co-creation are also important here. Forum Virium Helsinki has developed a manual for conducting open calls²⁵. An open call does require quite a bit of organisation so is especially suitable to do with a number of collaboration partners and a government agency, university or college.

Hackathon

A hackathon is an online or in-person event where you come up with several out-of-the-box solutions to a complex problem in a short period of time. Several teams compete against each other over one or two days for the winning innovative solution. It also involves setting challenges and providing criteria. Tech companies can respond with a proposal. Depending on the complexity of the problem, several rounds of judging take place to evaluate the proposals. In the end, a number of proposals are left over, which are developed practically in a short period of time (one to a few days) in co-creation with various rounds of testing. The target group can be involved at different phases of the hackathon. For example, they can be part of the jury and evaluate the proposals. When developing the proposals, different co-creation methods can be used to test prototypes together with the target group. Several descriptions of hackathons can be found on the internet. The Hackathon Handbook is one of them²⁶. A hackathon is an event that requires a lot of organisation. As with open calls, it is useful to seek collaboration with several partners.

Matching platform

A matching platform is a sustainable way of bringing supply and demand together. A good example is the Tech To The Rescue (TTTR) platform. Social organisations and target groups themselves can post challenges on this platform. Tech parties that want to offer their expertise pro or low bono to make a social difference also register on this platform. The TTTR organisation helps to refine the challenges and find the right partners. Its staff understands the social challenges and knows the different technology companies and their interests and expertise. This enables TTTR to find the right match between the different organisations.

5.1.3.5 Co-creation methods to involve the target group in assessing proposals.

Matching meeting

This method was deployed during the open calls in Porto. It can be used when multiple organisations want to work on a solution to the same challenge. A matching meeting takes place after a number of winners are selected from the open call. Different challenge owners (government, social organisations and the target group) are invited to a meeting where tech companies present their solutions. The challenges owners can now judge for themselves which solution best suits their challenge and the needs of the target audience. With this method, the winners are already chosen. The intention is that each proposal will actually be matched to a challenge owner.

²⁵ [Manuals - CommuniCity](#)

²⁶ [Hackathon Handbook](#)

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Composition of the jury

As already seen in the tips of this section, it is important to include sufficient expertise when it comes to finding the right partners. Jury members must be able to understand the challenge and the target group in order to assess whether the proposals have sufficient impact for the target group. To assess the proposals, you can ask experience experts and key figures from the community. They will also need to assess whether the proposer has sufficient understanding of co-creation and is willing to delve further into the challenge of the target group. For this you can also involve a social designer. A tech expert can assess whether the solution is feasible and of sufficient quality within given time and budget.

Another way of engaging the target group has been tried out in Breda, one of the pilot cities that joined the second open call. Their challenges were focused on issues of youngsters. The idea is to involve a target group by setting up an evaluation committee. In a session, the target group discusses the proposals. Collectively they will then decide which points will be assigned to the proposals. These points are entered as one vote in the evaluation system.

5.1.4 Development of the tech solution

5.1.4.1 Aim

To develop the technical solution.

5.1.4.2 Description – Design Thinking

This phase involves working together to develop the final tech solution that contributes to the challenge. This phase is again divided into different phases derived from the Design Thinking method. Design thinking is a creative, human-centred approach that can be used to tackle complex issues. Design thinking is an iterative, non-linear process that focuses on collaboration between designers and users. It brings to life innovative solutions based on how real users think, feel and behave.

Design thinking is a non-linear, iterative process that is used to understand users, challenge assumptions, redefine problems and create innovative solutions to prototype and test. Involving five phases—Empathise, Define, Ideate, Prototype and Test—it is most useful to tackle complex problems²⁷.

The first two phases of this process have already been partially completed in the first two phases of the process described in this deliverable, namely 5.1.1 Finding Challenges and 5.1.2 Articulating Needs. This does not mean that the first two phases of the Design Thinking process, Emphasize and Define, should be skipped. Starting with the Emphasize phase will help to let go of your own assumptions, to really immerse yourself in the target group, to understand their needs and to listen to their ideas.

²⁷ [Interaction Design Foundation – What is Design Thinking?](#)

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Figure 2: design thinking process

5.1.4.3 Tips

- Involve the target group itself, social organisations and/or key people who have contact with the target group and have a trusted relationship with them.
- Involve experts who understand design thinking and co-creation, social designers or social design students.
- Go to the target group, organise something in their close, familiar surroundings.
- Do not make the group too large.
- Use understandable language
- Avoid having professionals in the majority.
- Use accessible, understandable and visual methods

5.1.4.4 The five phases of design thinking

The different phases are not necessarily completed in chronological order. It is an iterative process that repeatedly returns to the previous phase to sharpen conclusions, refine ideas and test again. Results from the testing phase may, for example, offer new insights about users that lead to a new brainstorming session (Ideate) or the development of new prototypes (Prototype).

Phase 1 Empathise

This first phase of design thinking focuses on user-centric research. It aims to understand the target audience and the challenge they face as well as possible. The better you immerse yourself into the user's world the better the definition of the challenge and the needs there are to solve the challenge. Empathy is essential for problem solving and a human-centred design process. It allows designers to set aside their

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own assumptions and really understand users and their needs. Methods involving research and co-creation are used in this phase.

In this phase, the previously described methods from section 5.1.2.4 Methods to scope the challenge and section 5.1.2.5 co-creation methods to understand the target group can also be used.

5.1.4.4.1 Research methods to empathise

The research methods below are designed to collect data on the target group to better understand them.

Literature review

A literature review can provide initial context for the challenge to be solved. It provides insight into the expertise that already exists in this field that allows you to draw on previous research and experience²⁸.

Interview

Interviewing someone in their own environment gives you an insight into their motivations, habits and lifestyle. This method will provide you with a deeper context for the challenge you are trying to solve²⁹.

Five whys

Interviewing someone by sequentially asking the question why five times encourages reflection on deeper reasons for behaviour, attitudes, motives and needs³⁰.

Day in the life

In this type of research, the researcher follows a day in the life of the target group affected by the challenge. In this way you learn how they behave in their daily lives, which may be different from what they would say in an interview³¹.

5.1.4.4.2 Methods to immerse yourself in the target group

The methods below can be used after gathering information about the target group. They are used to immerse yourself the target group as a designer.

Empathy Map

An empathy map helps designers understand the perspective of their users by giving them an organised visual representation of the data they have collected about that person, incorporated into an empathy map. With this tool, designers can gain a better understanding of the needs and pain points of end users - all with the aim of creating tailored solutions that meet their needs³².

Persona's

A persona is a variation of the empathy map. It is a fictional character that represents an individual from the target group. This persona is created based on the data you have collected in your research and the

²⁸ [Design Method Toolkit – Literature review](#)

²⁹ [Design Kit - Interview](#)

³⁰ [Design Methods Finder – Five Whys](#)

³¹ [Design Method Toolkit – Day in the life](#)

³² [Design Method Toolkit – Empathy Map](#)

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themes or commonalities you have observed. This approach is designed to help you better understand your customers' needs, behaviours, experiences and goals³³.

Informance

Informance is a combination of role play, improvisation and body storming. It gives a deep insight into the client and goes beyond understanding the client's culture and motivations. It is really about an experience where the designer gets into the skin of the target group based on data collected from them. The designer takes on the life of the target group to really put themselves in their shoes³⁴.

5.1.4.4.3 Co-creation methods to empathise

The Sketch Game

This drawing exercise shows us how we can have different perspectives on different topics related to the challenge. In doing so, we reveal some of our unconscious assumptions and biases³⁵.

Drawing

Drawing is another way to put your thoughts in order. Asking questions about the challenge and asking participants to draw the answers gives a different picture of the issues than talking to each other. Discussing the drawing allows you to go deeper into the issue³⁶.

Computer Trust

This is a method to discover why people trust and distrust interactions with technology. In this way, ideas will eventually be developed that are user-friendly and fit the target audience³⁷.

Role Play

Role playing is used to gain an empathetic understanding of the target audience. By reenacting scenes and situations you are trying to improve, you can get a better sense of what the experience actually feels like and where you need to focus on in particular to make improvements³⁸.

Phase 2 Define

In this phase, you gather all the information you collected in the empathise phase. Here, you define the main problems within the challenge and the main needs of the target group and define a problem statement. To make sure you keep designing human-centred, it is important to keep the target group in mind as a starting point. The final problem statement should be defined from the user's perspective. A good problem statement is about the users themselves, what they would like (the ideal situation) and why this is not happening now (the problem). Always ensure that the target group continues to identify with the

³³ [Unalab Enoll - Persona](#)

³⁴ [Think Design - Informance](#)

³⁵ [HI Toolbox – The Sketch Game](#)

³⁶ [Design Kit – Draw it](#)

³⁷ [Inclusive: A Microsoft Design Toolkit – Activity- Cards](#)

³⁸ [Think Design – Role Play](#)

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analysis being made. Again, the target group can be involved in formulating the problem statement via co-creation.

5.1.4.4.3 Methods to define a problem statement

Haiku

Writing a problem statement in the form of a haiku is a fun, creative and easy way to keep the problems we need to solve in front of us and to focus on them so that we don't wander off looking for ideas and solutions? Creating a haiku reinforces the problem in our minds and fixes it in our long-term memory³⁹.

Frame the challenge

This template will help you reframe the problem into an inspiring challenge. This rewrites your core problem and translates it into an opportunity. This gives you space to think about solutions in the Ideate phase⁴⁰.

Problem Statement Template

Completing a problem statement template helps you get the real question behind the problem in focus.⁴¹

5.1.4.4.4 Co-creation methods to define a problem statement

Ishiwaka fishbone diagram

A fishbone diagram is a tool to classify the different causes of a problem. it allows us to identify the main causes of a problem. The method uses brainstorming with a mind map template⁴².

How might we questions

With this co-creation method, you turn the problem areas you have identified into a "how might we" question. These questions are positive. They open the door to different solutions to a problem. It gives you the perfect framework for innovative thinking⁴³.

Phase 3 Ideate

In this third phase of design thinking, as many ideas as possible are collected based on the knowledge of the target group, the challenge and the problem statement. It is therefore about quantity, not quality. In design thinking, you don't have to come up with the best solution right away. Thinking out of the box is allowed. The weirdest ideas can lead to the best solutions. So initially, it is not important whether the ideas are possible and fit the needs of the target group. Some ideas that don't fit can lead to other ideas that do. So don't be limited. At the end of the ideate phase, filter and test the ideas for quality and see if they fit the needs of the target group. Several ideas can also be combined into one solution. The ideate phase is creative and full of opportunities for co-creation.

³⁹ [How to write a memorable problem statement - Neil Cooper](#)

⁴⁰ [Prosperity Now - Frame the Challenge](#)

⁴¹ [Uxspot.io - Problem-Statement-Template](#)

⁴² [Tech Target - Ishiwaka Fishbone Diagram](#)

⁴³ [Hyper Island Toolbox – How might we questions](#)

5.1.4.4.5 Co-creation methods to gather ideas

Brainwriting

Brainwriting is a method for generating a lot of ideas in a very short time. Because everyone is writing down ideas for themselves, it is a method to involve even the less assertive. The sheets of paper on which the ideas are written can also be passed around. The next person then associates the ideas of the previous person. In this way you can create loads of ideas.⁴⁴

Yes, and

This method can be used to continue associating on other people's ideas. It prevents too many objections being raised in a brainstorm when new ideas are generated. This reduces creative blockages and allows shared ideas to emerge.⁴⁵

Worst possible ideas

Looking for the worst possible ideas breaks the fixed idea that every suggestion must be good. Looking for good ideas can cause you to get stuck or to keep generating ideas that already exist. Coming up with bad ideas puts you in a different mindset and creates a different energy through which you gather completely different ideas. Coming up with the opposite of the worst ideas will bring you back to good ideas.⁴⁶

Crazy 8's

Crazy 8's challenges people to come up with ideas quickly and creatively using simple sketches. The aim is to go beyond the first idea, which is often the least innovative, and generate a wide range of solutions to your challenge.⁴⁷

Sensorial

This brainstorming method helps you generate ideas that are outside your normal comfort zone. With sensorial you use your senses and develop ideas by associating on sense, vision, scent, feeling, hearing, and tasting.⁴⁸

5.1.4.4.6 Co-creation methods to select ideas

Dot voting

Dot voting is a quick way to reach a consensus on the most interesting ideas in a large collection of ideas. Dot voting uses gut feeling and the wisdom of the crowd to quickly make an initial mix of ideas. Once the initial shuffle is done, methods are used to look more closely at the most important ideas.⁴⁹

⁴⁴ [TISDD - Brainwriting](#)

⁴⁵ [Innovation Bazar - Yes, and](#)

⁴⁶ [Interaction Design Foudation – Worst Possible Idea](#)

⁴⁷ [Design Sprint Kit – Crazy 8's](#)

⁴⁸ [Design Method Toolkit - Sensorial](#)

⁴⁹ [Design Method Toolkit – Dot Voting](#)

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Benny Hill Sorting (Thirty Five)

This tool helps to quickly select the most interesting ideas from a large pool of possibilities. As well as creating a ranking of ideas, it also creates a sense of ownership. This can be useful if the group is having difficulty letting go of their ideas.⁵⁰

Six thinking hats

The six thinking hats is a method for looking at collected ideas from different perspectives. In this way, you gain insight into the feasibility and desirability of ideas and can start making a selection for the prototype phase.⁵¹

The Walt Disney method

The Walt Disney method allows you to develop ideas until it is suitable for prototyping. The method is based on the interplay of three roles: the dreamer (visionary, idea provider), the realist (creator) and the critic (quality manager). They all look at the ideas from their own perspective and constantly hone it.⁵²

Phase 4 Prototype

In the Ideate phase, a number of good ideas are selected that provide part of the solution to the target group's challenge. In the prototype phase, you try out these ideas in a small-scale and low-threshold way. These are simple tests with the target group in which the prototype is tested via a dummy of, for example, paper, cardboard or lego or a clickable prototype. The prototypes are often parts of the solution that are tested to find out what the user thinks of the solution, whether it works in practice and what the user's behavior is. In this phase, there is often a lot of feedback on what works and what does not. You then regularly have to go back to the define or ideate phase to sharpen the problem statement and adjust the ideas. Once the solutions have been tested and improved several times, you can move on to more advanced prototypes in the Testphase.

5.1.4.4.7 (Co-creation) methods to prototype

Paper Prototyping

Paper prototyping is mainly used to create and test interfaces in an accessible way. It allows you to quickly visualise basic concepts and test them with end users for potential usability issues. It is also a way to co-design with the target group. Paper prototyping together provides you with new design ideas that meet the needs of the target group.⁵³

Cardboard prototyping

Cardboard prototypes are a common low-fidelity method of simulating three-dimensional physical objects and environments. for example, the interior of a retail environment, a ticket machine, furniture, tools and smaller props. Prototypes are built quickly, usually from cheap paper and cardboard. Other equally user-

⁵⁰ [TISDD – Benny Hill Sorting thirty five](#)

⁵¹ [Interaction Design Foundation – Six Thinking Hats](#)

⁵² [Design Methods Finder - Walt Disney Method](#)

⁵³ [Design Methods Finder – Paper Prototyping](#)

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friendly materials such as foam core, plasticine or duct tape often complement the mix of materials. The cardboard prototype helps to adapt the initial idea and explore its details, strengths and weaknesses.⁵⁴ There are many tutorials on the internet explaining how to make a cardboard prototype.⁵⁵

Lego prototypes

Lego bricks are used to quickly assemble and customise a rough model of a physical product. Lego prototypes can be used to mimic the actual size and shape of a proposed physical product. By building it with Lego, you can determine its dimensions. By letting your users build it themselves, you encourage them to experiment. People open their minds, become more relaxed in their interactions with each other and reveal more of what is beneath the surface.⁵⁶

Clickable prototypes

A clickable prototype is an interactive representation of the interface design. It is not the final design or product. The person using a clickable prototype can perform all interactive actions, such as navigating through the interface. Clickable prototypes help test critical features. The prototype can be tested for user experience and changes can be proposed.⁵⁷

Phase 5 Test

The test phase is similar to the prototype phase. In both phases, you focus on usability testing. In the prototype phase, you still do this with different parts of your solution in the form of a prototype. In the test phase, you put all these prototypes together. So you test the entire solution. Again, this phase is iterative. You may very well find that something does not work or does not meet the needs of the target group. You then have to go through several phases again until you finally have the ideal solution and proven that everything works, a Proof Of Concept (POC). This is what you actually develop.

5.1.4.4.8 Co-creation methods to test

High fidelity prototypes

A high-fidelity prototype is used when a lot of feedback has already come back to the low-fidelity prototypes and the designs have been modified. It is a detailed and realistic representation of a design concept that is close to the final solution. These prototypes are usually created with advanced tools and technologies, such as 3D models, renderings, animations or interactive software.⁵⁸

5.1.5 Implementation and maintenance

5.1.5.1 Aim

To implement a technical solution in a system and to keep it up to date.

⁵⁴ [Stem Senior Engineering – Cardboard Prototyping](#)

⁵⁵ [Teleskola – Cardboard Modelling](#)

⁵⁶ [Learning Loop – Lego Prototype](#)

⁵⁷ [Educative – Clickable Prototype](#)

⁵⁸ [Medium - High Fidelity Prototyping](#)

5.1.5.2 Description

Once the technical solution is tested and ready to go, you can release it to the target group. If the technical solution is digital, your product should be embedded in the technical environment of the system, such as a computer or mobile phone. Explore the devices your target group uses. They may not have the latest version and the most up-to-date devices. Consider the target group's financial situation. Social organisations or the target group are far from being able to pay a commercial rate. Make sure the solution can be maintained. Think about open source solutions, updates that do not overload the system, and maintenance subscriptions that are affordable for the target group.

5.1.5.3 Tips

- Take the financial situation of your target group into account.
- Make sure your solution can be implemented on the devices used by the target group.
- Keeps maintenance simple and affordable
- Think of open source solutions
- Use social financing to cover costs (see section 6.3.1.1)
- Try to scale up by developing a solution that is also interesting for other target groups (see section 6.3.2.2)

5.1.6 Adoption

5.1.6.1 Aim

Commissioning of the tech solution by the target group

5.1.6.2 Description

Adoption of tech solutions by marginalised groups requires a different effort than the usual marketing techniques used to publicise a new product. For example, a homeless person will not be online very often and will have to find out through the homeless shelter that a tool has been developed that lists places to sleep, wash and eat. Marginalised groups who have little or no confidence in using digital tools need intensive counselling to become familiar with the solution. People who do not have money to buy a mobile phone, tablet or laptop will need to be provided for. Blind and deaf people will need to be informed through their own dedicated network. The adoption of these tech solutions therefore requires specific channels and networks to actually put the developed solution into use. As described earlier, it helps if the target group itself is intensively involved in defining the challenge and developing the solutions. If the end product really works then they are the best ambassadors to further market the product. As a tech developer, you need the target group, civil society organisations, key people and experts by experience themselves to publicise the product, gain trust and guide and instruct users.

5.1.6.3 Tips

- Involve the target group, civil society organisations and experts by experience in the adoption of the developed tech solution.
- Keep in mind that money and time are scarce with the above-mentioned partners.
- Again, delve well into the target group, where to reach them, who they trust and whether they need (intensive) guidance to start using the tool.

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- Go to the users and let them try out the tech solution in their own living environment.

5.2 Incremental improvement

This deliverable has been written with the knowledge gained from the interviews, workshops, meetings and pilots of the first round of CommuniCity. As long as CommuniCity is running, the process described in chapter 5 can be improved with the experience gained from the next rounds of open calls and pilots. There are also learning points that we can apply directly to the CommuniCity open call and pilot process itself. With the tips and (co-creation) methods provided in chapter 5, a growing toolbox can be developed that can be used in the next projects where co-creation with marginalised groups is expected. There are still bottlenecks that cannot be solved within CommuniCity. In Chapter 6, we make suggestions for research and follow-up projects to work towards a solution.

5.2.1 Schedule for updates and version control

Version	Date
V1	29/02/2024
V2 (with lessons learned from second round open call and pilots)	30/06/2024
V3 (with lessons learned from third round open call and pilots)	30/06/2025
<i>Note 1: If necessary additional updates can be published between the rounds (e.g. v1.2, v1.3, v2.1)</i>	
<i>Note 2: V3 will also include a summary of the changes made between versions 1.0–3.0.</i>	

5.2.2. Learning points for the current process within CommuniCity

Based on the experience of the first round, several adjustments to the open calls and piloting process have already been made. A number of adjustments are tangential to this deliverable. Below is a list of these adjustments and some suggestions to improve the current process. These suggestions focus on the mission of this deliverable: matching the needs of citizens to solutions of tech providers.

1. **Good practices:** Experiences with prior projects and within the pilots of CommuniCity already produced a list of good practices that should be adopted when working with marginalised groups to avoid disappointment and abuse. This list can be found on the “read this first” pages accompanying the open calls on the CommuniCity site. These good practices have a strong connection to the process described in chapter 5 in this deliverable when it comes to co-creation and impact. A list is one way of highlighting these good practices. It is important to keep highlighting these good practices and pay attention to this list. During several discussions and meetings including the kick-off meetings, they are now being discussed by the various participating parties.
2. **Co-creation sessions:** Co-creation is not yet common for every tech company. The proposals submitted to the challenges describe various co-creation methodologies. Regularly, these include common research methods that offer insight into the target group and the challenges but do not require real involvement and input from the target group. Within CommuniCity, co-creation is very important with marginalised groups at the centre of attention. Their challenge, needs and experiences are the starting point of the design of the tech solution. Co-creation methods should therefore always aim to involve the target group throughout the design process. Amsterdam has started offering co-

creation sessions for the winning proposals. These sessions are being further developed in cooperation with Porto Domus Social. These sessions highlight the importance of co-creation with marginalised groups and give an impression of what forms of co-creation exist.

3. **Identifying and Specifying challenges:** Throughout the deliverable we have described the different approaches taken by the different cities to identify and specify challenges. Porto and Helsinki have a more sustainable relationship with civil society organisations and municipal departments with which they identify and formulate challenges. Amsterdam is looking for collaboration with various organisations and also residents' organisations to get closer to the target group. Porto has experimented with co-creation to explore different themes. In sections 5.1.1 Detecting Challenges and 5.1.2 Articulating the needs, co-creation methods are described to identify and specify challenges together with the target group and/or social organisation. It would be interesting to analyse the different approaches and the effect on the final solutions to provide better advice on the scope and feasibility of challenges in a pilot environment such as that of CommuniCity.

4. **Evaluation of proposals:** This deliverable stresses several times the importance of understanding the target audience and their challenge. Impact and co-creation are important criteria within CommuniCity that impose conditions on the proposals submitted in response to the challenges. The proposals submitted in the open calls show that Impact and co-creation are still interpreted in multiple ways. Interviews, surveys and focus groups are submitted as co-creation methodologies. For the evaluation it is important to have sufficient expertise to be able to assess whether these conditions are met and how to assess it as a jury member. This means that there must be sufficient knowledge of the challenges, the target groups, impact and co-creation. It would be a great opportunity if Helsinki, Porto and Amsterdam could pool their experiences and develop a good instructional workshop for this to be offered to all cities in the third round.

5.2.3 Remaining bottlenecks

During our research for CommuniCity, we came across a number of bottlenecks that, if addressed, would improve the process described in Chapter 5. These are:

- Awareness of the value of technology for social challenges
- Financing tech for marginalised groups
- Implementation and maintenance

During the pilots within CommuniCity and in the various consortium meetings, several ethical issues when working with marginalised groups were raised. Deliverable D2.1 'Guidelines for Marginalised and Vulnerable Communities' discusses these in detail. These ethical issues are also closely related to this deliverable. That is why we also pay attention to them here.

CommuniCity itself and the pilots within the project contribute in part to raising awareness of the value of tech for marginalised groups and thus contribute in part to solving the bottlenecks. However, these bottlenecks cannot all be solved within this project as they are sustainable in nature and sustainable solutions need to be found. In Chapter 6, we discuss these bottlenecks in more detail and describe suggestions for further research and possible projects in which to work towards a solution.

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5.2.4 Toolbox for co-creation with Marginalised groups

The process in chapter 5 contains various co-creation methods appropriate to the different phases of the process and when working with marginalised groups. Some examples are given per phase, but many more methods exist. For the third round within CommuniCity and future open calls and pilots, it is valuable to develop an accessible and further expandable toolbox that helps all stakeholders to develop tech that truly contributes to social challenges of marginalised groups, addresses their needs and is understandable and usable. This toolbox can be developed in collaboration with ENoLL and published on their site.

6 Remaining Bottlenecks

Earlier in Chapters 2 and 3, it became clear that awareness of tech's potential for social challenges, implementation and funding are important preconditions for enhancing the uptake of tech solutions both by marginalised communities and by associations working with these groups. We were unable to find sustainable solutions for these main bottlenecks during the pilots within CommuniCity. However, we did pick up ideas on awareness, implementation and funding in our research. In this chapter, we list some of these ideas and make suggestions for a follow-up. Not all these ideas have yet been given a place to develop them further. Within CommuniCity, we will discuss whether they connect to other deliverables yet to be developed. Furthermore, we will explore if there are opportunities to implement them as part of other European, national or municipal programmes. We hope to have planted a seed with these suggestions for further research and new projects, so that they can be deployed somewhere when the opportunity arises.

Chapter 5 describes a process from identifying challenges from marginalised groups to adopting the tech solution. This addresses the second main bottleneck encountered in our research. Within CommuniCity, we were able to try out part of this process in practice. We managed to go through the first 4 phases during the open calls and pilot phase. Sometimes the pilot ended in a prototype, sometimes a final product was delivered. However, phase 5, implementation and maintenance and phase 6, adoption, have not been part of the process within the pilots in CommuniCity. Partly this is the responsibility of the challenge owner who deploys the tech solution, partly of the tech company that developed the tech solution. Nevertheless, bottlenecks regarding these phases also emerged in our research.

In Chapter 2 on marginalised groups and Chapter 4 on co-creation, the ethical issues surrounding working with marginalised target groups are already briefly touched upon. We will also discuss these further in this chapter.

6.1 Awareness of the value of tech for social challenges

This section addresses the first bottleneck in this deliverable.

1. Tech is generally not yet sufficiently seen as a solution to social challenges of marginalised groups.

Everything you give attention to grows. This is already visible in the difference between attention to e-health and lagging technology for marginalised groups with social challenges. The reason behind the growing development of e-health is efficiency and money saving. It takes the burden off the healthcare system. There is also an increasing focus from the government and media on prevention and the physical and mental health benefits of a fit life. There is a clear urgency on this topic.

Social issues also have urgency. They too can have a profound impact on individuals' well-being, both mental and physical problems. Preventing poverty and debt, preventing bullying and crime, strengthening social networks and reducing loneliness are of great value for individuals themselves and for society as a whole. Here, too, tech solutions can contribute greatly. However, the link between tech and social value, leading to more empowerment and a better social position in life, is more difficult to establish in this case.

With social issues, the challenges are more complex and often more sensitive. Because the direct link to impact is harder to establish, effectiveness and preventive effects are difficult to demonstrate. It does not become visible how much money is saved, and investment, subsidies and funds lag behind.

A lot of knowledge does already exist about the social value of social networks and the role social media has in them. Community apps help prevent loneliness and promote physical and mental health. It is important to remain mindful of the negative aspects such as cyberbullying, misinformation and sexual harassment. It is worth expanding this knowledge further to include other social functions of tech, exchange this knowledge, pool it and show good examples. If we can make the value of tech as a contribution to the solution of social issues visible, the attention will naturally grow. This still requires some development.

Chapter 2 already gives an impetus for advice on how to highlight the importance of social challenges. Going deeper into marginalised groups, their position and their issues gives a better picture of what is going on. Making visible the impact of these issues on society also gives a greater sense of urgency. The next step is to jointly explore with various stakeholders how tech can contribute to improving the position of marginalised groups with social challenges and make these examples visible.

6.1.1. Next steps for research and projects

In practice, this means setting up a network, organising conferences and meetings, sharing knowledge and generating attention among politicians and media. Projects such as CommuniCity, the Belgian project Amai Vlaanderen⁵⁹ and the platform Tech To the Rescue contribute to this awareness. Such projects deserve replication and improvement in a growing learning curve to raise awareness of the possibilities of tech for marginalised groups. With more emphasis on involvement of the target group itself and knowledge dissemination.

We can also learn a lot from adoption and acceptance methodologies in e-health for healthcare workers. By organising knowledge-sharing meetings, presenting existing working tech solutions and creating VR patient environments, healthcare is trying to raise awareness among their employees.

6.2 Implementation and Maintenance

This section addresses the third bottleneck in this deliverable.

3. Unfamiliarity with tech often makes it difficult for civil society organisations to implement and maintain developed tools.

Among the bottlenecks described in section 1.3, implementation and maintenance is one of the issues social organisations working with marginalised groups face. Unfamiliarity with tech makes it hard to determine which parties to partner with, what systems you need, how to make them secure and how to

⁵⁹ [Amai!](#)

handle privacy-sensitive information. Another important issue is how to deal with AI and the negative consequences of algorithms. OASC MIM5 (Minimal Interoperability Mechanisms) on Fair and Transparent Artificial Intelligence addresses this issue⁶⁰. For smaller organisations and NGOs that rely on funds and grants, it is difficult to bring in expertise and pay for the implementation and maintenance of tech solutions. Often, the scale of maintenance and development of tech tools is not large enough to employ someone to do so. As a result, social organisations do not have sufficient expertise to determine whether a tech solution is interesting for their societal challenges and who they should partner with to develop the solution.

6.2.1 Next steps for research and projects

There may be several smaller social organisations with the same issue. One solution could be to outsource this task and set up a central maintenance point, either for organisations working with a particular target group (e.g. homeless people) or for any non-governmental organisation. In future projects it would be interesting to research and try out whether a group of NGOs, with or without government help, could set up a separate organisation that would have various technical solutions developed and implemented, maintained and managed. Commercial companies use maintenance as a service. This would also be an interesting solution for social organisations, if affordable. Adding 'open source' as a requirement when commissioning technical solutions or setting up open calls would also facilitate such a central maintenance point.

6.3 Financing tech for marginalised groups

This section addresses the fourth bottleneck in this deliverable.

4. Having a technical solution developed is often too expensive for marginalised target groups and civil society organisations (CSOs)

Funding is an issue that affects all phases of tech development for marginalised groups. As described in section 2.1.4, development often lacks a revenue model and CSOs typically rely on temporary funding opportunities such as funds and grants. This means that a tech solution to a challenge may be developed, but then cannot be implemented and maintained. In addition, users themselves are not always able to pay for a technological solution. Marginalised groups consist of a relatively small number of people, so the market for technological solutions to their problems is quite small. Put simply, there often does not seem to be a business case.

As funding is a recurring issue in social challenges, we delved deeper into this topic during our research to find solutions. Besides our interviews with CSOs and the target group, we introduced our issue at various conferences and events during workshops and collected ideas. We also found several overviews and suggestions on the internet that point the way in the forest of grants, funds, innovation budgets and open calls. We can point to some of them here but it would take us too far to create a complete overview.

⁶⁰ [OASC- MIM5- Transparency](#)

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Not all of the ideas and suggestions we raised offer a sustainable solution. Several ideas are temporary structures that can finance part of the process described in Chapter 5. This often involves the development of the tech solution, but excludes adoption. Adoption might be achievable with temporary budgets but is frequently outside the scope of the application. Implementation, maintenance and improvement of the tech solution remains a major problem. This requires sustainable resources and deployment of expertise. And that is hardly ever funded.

Below, we describe the various ideas that have come to us for 'funding' the development of tech for marginalised groups. These ideas range from financial solutions to free use of expertise, study assignments and social return constructions.

6.3.1 Different ways of raising money

There are multiple ways to fund tech development for marginalised groups. This could be for the development of a final product, but also to find out what is needed through experimentation or to test and tweak an existing product.

6.3.1.1 Grants

The following proposals focus mainly on large European projects in which governments work together with civil society organisations and knowledge institutions. The resulting projects, such as ComuniCity, then provide opportunities for smaller companies to get involved. For the development of technological solutions together with a target group or social organisation, opportunities for smaller companies in various countries can be found on national fund pages. However, this remains a search and there is no overview yet of technology development for marginalised groups.

- EU Funding Toolkit: <https://euclidnetwork.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/european-funding-toolkit.pdf>
- EU Calls for proposals: <https://euclidnetwork.eu/portfolio-posts/eu-calls-for-proposals/>
- ESF: <https://ec.europa.eu/esf/home.jsp>
- Horizon Europe: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en
- Dutch ISDN fund: [SIDN fonds : een sterk internet voor iedereen](#)

6.3.1.2 Crowdfunding

Nowadays, crowdfunding is a fairly common way of financing. When an organisation thinks that a technical solution can bring a lot of benefit to a certain target group, they can place their project on a crowdfunding platform. Crowdfunding is especially suitable when the goal is clear and limited. It may therefore be suitable to have a technical solution developed, but not to maintain it. It is a way of funding in which local networks raise money for a social purpose that benefits the neighbourhood. It is also well suited to specific

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topics or themes. The funders themselves then have a strong involvement or interest in the topic in question.

6.3.1.3 Social impact bonds

The Social Impact Bond (SIB) is a financing instrument in which private money is used to solve social issues. Clear agreements are made in advance about objectives and results that must be achieved for the target group. If these objectives and results are achieved, the investor gets his money back with a return. If that is not the case, the investor bears the risk. With Social Impact Bonds, the needs of the target group are central instead of the revenue model. This makes it easier for governments to invest in large social projects without running any risks.

This financial instrument may in some cases be suitable, particularly when dealing with voluminous and expensive government tasks. It would be worth further exploring the suitability of this financial instrument when looking for tech solutions for people in vulnerable or marginalised positions.

6.3.2 The revenue model

There are also tech solutions that do make enough money because they have enough paying customers.

6.3.2.1 The prevailing revenue model

Some people belonging to vulnerable or marginalised groups are wealthy enough to purchase technology. In these cases it may be an option to charge users for using the solution. There may also be a social model in which the tech solution is sold at a profit and partly for a social price.

6.3.2.2 Scaling up by combining target groups

Explained above, it can be difficult to recoup investments if only a small number of people benefit from them. As a result, investments lag behind. But in some cases, it is possible to increase the number of people who benefit by working together across municipal or country borders.

Another way to increase the number of users is to explore whether people other than the original target group could also benefit from the solution. In one of the Amsterdam pilots a speech to text solution is being developed for hearing impaired and deaf people. The developer is exploring whether the solution could also be useful for tourists. This makes the solution more scalable and affordable.

6.3.3 For social value

There are several tech companies that are happy to contribute to solving a social challenge for free. Sometimes these are large companies that consider social impact important from intrinsic motivation and from a marketing perspective. Smaller start-ups are also happy to contribute. For them it is an opportunity to gain experience and make a name for themselves. Their investment is mainly in the form of free labour. It is also interesting for educational institutions to give their students the opportunity to gain experience. The government often looks for opportunities to stimulate social impact.

6.3.3.1 Developing Value Cases

When developing tech solutions for issues of marginalised groups, it may seem that there is no profit to be made and that the needed investment would be too high. But for some issues, it may be worthwhile to develop tech solutions although it may at first sight seem too expensive. If there is no business case, perhaps there is a 'value case'. The benefits that the solution would bring to people of a particular target group may not be easy to express in money but may be very valuable. For example, a tech solution might increase the autonomy of a target group.

It would be insightful to describe a value case instead of a business case. There are several methodologies to build a value case, such as Social Return On Investment (SROI)⁶¹, the Most Significant Change⁶², the Social AEX⁶³ and the Value case method of TNO (Dutch organisation for applied natural science research)⁶⁴. Social value is hereby converted into money. This provides insight into how much cost can be avoided through preventive results. Which instrument is used where, depends on the size of the project and the expected social impact. Experience remains that funding streams are often deployed in the short term for immediate visible results. Investing in projects because generating social value prevents further problems and costs is generally not integrated in the balance sheet of a budget, making it difficult to invest in estimated social value.⁶⁵ Making social value visible then mainly has the function of engaging companies and funds willing to make a contribution out of intrinsic motivation, branding considerations or because it is in line with a fund's social values.

6.3.3.2 Working with students

Universities and other educational institutions may be very interested in working with local authorities to give their students experience in designing solutions to real life issues. It can be motivating and educational for students to apply themselves to a social problem. Students can also be part of the research by exploring a possible solution and discover whether a direction taken is worth investing in.

6.3.3.3 Social return

Social return is part of tender processes and is often laid down in the purchasing policy of larger organisations. A contractual condition is included in the tender process, whereby the company that receives the contract has an obligation to give something back to society. In general, social return is used to reduce the distance to the labor market for people from specific target groups. There are more and more examples of companies giving their employees hours to use their expertise, for example, on financial issues of smaller CSOs or in debt assistance.

⁶¹ When issuing purchase orders, public procurers can encourage or require contractors to employ vulnerable groups when implementing the contract. This measure can also be used to create social and sustainable impact.

⁶² The Most Significant Change (MSC) technique is a form of participatory monitoring and evaluation. It involves the collection and selection of stories of change, produced by programme or project stakeholders.

⁶³ The Social AEX gives initiatives and companies insight into social impact by generating a model based on input data (Social Handprint).

⁶⁴ The Value Case method helps consortia make decisions in sustainable innovations and transitions. The values of all parties in the consortium are carefully, independently and objectively identified.

⁶⁵ [Social Issues - How do you measure the value of social interventions?](#)

6.3.3.4 A social tech platform for social issues

A solution worth mentioning is the existing platform Tech to The Rescue. They pair social challenges from CSOs with tech companies eager to tackle social issues. In doing so, they have set up a database of tech companies that want to contribute pro bono or low bono to a social challenge. In that same database, they collect recurring challenges and appropriate solutions. For the major challenges of our time such as environmental poverty and health issues, they organise international hackathons. In this way, a great network is set up between NGOs and tech companies and a wealth of knowledge is created that can be reused.

6.3.4 Next steps for research and projects

Above are a number of solutions that are worth investigating further to see what they can mean for solving the bottlenecks described in chapter 1. Within CommuniCity there is no opportunity to try this out. To take these learnings a step further, we would like to do some more research and try them out in practice. For government organisations and a European programme organisation, Value case methodologies and Social Impact Bonds would be the most interesting to explore further.

6.4 Adoption

Adopting a tech application can be 'easy' if the user sees the benefits, is used to using technology, or because there is no other option, for example because physical counters are disappearing. Such as banking apps, popular music apps, games and fitness trackers. It is a different story if the user is not used to dealing with technology, does not have the money to purchase it or cannot be reached online. In those cases, common marketing campaigns such as events, promotional teams, advertisements and social media campaigns do not have the desired effect.

In Chapter 4 on co-creation, it becomes clear that it is important for the target group to see themselves in the challenge and to be involved in the solution. Then there is a sense of ownership and support for the use and adoption of the tech solution. It makes a difference if the target group understands the importance of using the tool, but this does not mean that they will be able to use it or that the whole target group will be reached. There are a number of challenges to implementing tech solutions for marginalised target groups:

1. **Intensive guidance:** For various target groups, the adoption requires guidance to learn how to use the technology.
2. **Trust:** If you are not used to working with technology, it takes time to gain trust before you actually start working with it.
3. **Accessibility:** The target group cannot be reached with major campaigns but moves in local networks. It takes more time to reach many people.
4. **Availability:** Various target groups for whom the technology has been developed do not have access to that technology due to a lack of financial resources. For example, they do not have a mobile phone, tablet or computer. These will then have to be distributed through social programs.

6.4.1 Next steps for research and projects

The important factors that play a role here are time and money. The section on finances already shows that this is often lacking among social organisations and the target group itself. During our research, we were not able to sufficiently discuss the experiences with adoption of technology among marginalised groups. Articles have been written about it and various social organisations have experience with it. It is worthwhile to share and bundle these experiences more and also to have governments and tech organisations think about increasing accessibility to the tech solutions that are being developed.

6.5 Ethical issues when piloting with target groups

Collaboration with marginalised groups can lead to disappointment and damage to trust. This often has to do with the extent to which we delve into their situation and take their voice and ideas seriously. The expectations we create and the appreciation we have for their knowledge and input are very important. People in a marginalised position already have a physical, mental and/or social disadvantage compared to people in a favourable situation and a better position in society. In a collaborative situation it can happen that this inequality in position is unintentionally confirmed again. We assume that they can get to a place easily, are used to speaking in meetings, know exactly what they want, feel comfortable and understand everything that is said. However, there is often discomfort and shame because they cannot participate in the meetings, workshops and expert meetings that are often organised.

The knowledge that people in a marginalised position bring with them is different from the knowledge we get from media, analyses and research. They are experts by experience and know better than anyone what it is like to not have a home, not be able to pay your bills, not be able to put enough food on the table for your children or to be discriminated against. These are often difficult topics to discuss. It requires an empathetic approach to ensure that their experiences are made visible and taken seriously. Taking their experiences and living environment as a starting point for the design of the solution usually leads to very different ideas and input than we are used to. And that in turn leads to solutions that are useful for the target group.

There is a lot of information available about the do's and don'ts in collaboration with marginalised groups. There is plenty to find out about the situation they find themselves in, the accumulation of problems that this leads to and the social consequences thereof. There is also a lot of information about co-creation and design thinking methods that creatively facilitate collaboration and innovation. However, these methods are still mainly focused on product development. The involvement of the target group is usually limited to interviews, surveys and focus groups where the designer gathers information about the target group's needs and behaviours. With this information, the designers' team goes through the phases from emphasize to ideate without involving the target group. The end user only has a real influence at the prototype phase, when different sub-solutions are tested. They are often not involved in defining the problem and generating ideas. This means that projects set up to support marginalised target groups generally do not spend enough time really getting to know and understand them. Often we talk about them instead of with

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them and develop solutions without them. Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS) will elaborate on this in deliverable 6.4 Impact analysis of the solutions.

6.5.1 Next steps for research and projects

In practice, it is important to introduce an ethical standard in projects that are set up for marginalised groups so that the collaborating parties have a common understanding of the collaboration and the importance of involving and understanding the target group. An example is the Tada manifesto⁶⁶ in Amsterdam. It has six values, like inclusiveness and humanitarianism, that guide the responsible use of data and the responsible design of technology in the city. It is signed by eight organisations working with innovation and data. These values are their starting points when developing tech innovations that use data. Similarly, (european) principles can be established based on agreed values when it comes to developing tech solutions in cooperation with marginalised groups. In the field of AI, MIM5 is already working on this topic within CommuniCity. MIM5, which is supported by the OASC, is concerned with supporting automated decision-making through algorithmic systems that are trustworthy, fair and transparent. To mitigate risks, a European standard for procurement rules is being developed with several European countries.⁶⁷ Another inspiring example is The Cities Coalition for Digital Rights. More than 50 cities worldwide are helping each other develop digital rights-based policy-making. Among other things, the coalition is working on legal, ethical and operational frameworks to promote human rights in digital environments.⁶⁸

The list of good practices made available for the open calls and pilots within CommuniCity and the Key ethical points compiled in Deliverable 2.1 can provide a handle for developing an ethical standard.

Furthermore, Deliverable 2.5 includes an iterative approach to developing a framework for inclusive and ethical tech piloting. Drawing from a diverse set of ethics principles, exemplary frameworks for co-creative processes in piloting and intersectionality, the initial framework will be updated based on collected feedback by the end of the project.

To understand and apply these frameworks, it would be valuable to introduce knowledge sessions and toolkits at the beginning and during projects to make them practical. The co-creation methods shared in this deliverable can help make this practice tangible.

⁶⁶ [tada city](#)

⁶⁷ [OASC MIM5 transparency](#)

⁶⁸ [Cities for Digital Rights](#)

7 Conclusion

If we want to design technology solutions that meet the needs of marginalised groups, we need to immerse ourselves in those needs. A pilot environment like CommuniCity's sets limits on time and financial resources in addressing complex challenges. The experiences gained from interviews, workshops, pilots and discussions within CommuniCity show that developing a tech solution to societal challenges of a complex and sensitive nature takes time and money. Complex challenges require specific co-creation methods to gain the trust of the target audience, accurately specify and define the challenges they face and devise solutions that meet their needs.

In our research, we found that there was a growing need for government, social organisations and marginalised groups to be fully involved in the development of technology solutions, from start to finish. In particular, technology companies wanted to understand the target groups and the challenges they face. This can be achieved by applying co-creation. Within CommuniCity, co-creation is one of the four criteria on which the proposals of tech parties responding to the challenges in the open call rounds are evaluated. In co-creation, all participants have an equal influence on the process and the final outcome. The conditions for successful co-creation are equality of participants, reciprocity, openness and trust.

The challenges from the different cities of Porto, Helsinki and Amsterdam in the first open call vary in complexity. Sometimes they are single issues such as a speech-to-speech translation (Amsterdam) or improving existing alarm systems for the safety of elderly people in their homes (Helsinki). Other challenges are more complex, such as reducing loneliness among elderly people (Porto) or unemployment (Helsinki). A large proportion of the technology companies that submitted proposals already had an existing technology solution that was adapted to the needs of the target group during the pilot phase. This was to be expected given the limited time and funding available. In the case of a simple problem, this worked well. For more complex challenges, the limitations of the existing solution were an obstacle to developing a truly appropriate solution.

The proposals submitted and the pilots show different levels of expertise in co-creation. Some define co-creation as conducting interviews, surveys and focus groups where the target group only has input. Others use methods that give the target group more influence and an equal position in the design process. Collaboration with marginalised groups can face challenges leading to disappointment and trust damage, often stemming from inadequate understanding and appreciation of their situation and ideas. The unique knowledge brought by those in marginalised positions, based on personal experiences, differs from conventional sources. Empathy is essential to recognise and take seriously their experiences of homelessness, financial hardship or discrimination. Designing solutions from their perspective leads to different, more effective ideas.

What we have learnt from this is that a good design process, where a solution is created that truly meets the needs of the target group, requires them to be equally involved from start to finish. From defining the challenge to adapting the solution. The process described in this deliverable is based on human-centred design (design thinking). Design thinking methods focus on audience engagement and deepening understanding of the issue at stake. The process in this deliverable is divided into six phases: 1. Detecting

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challenges, 2. Articulating the needs, 3. Matching tech parties, 4. Development of the tech solution, 5. Implementation and Maintenance, 6. Adoption. The fourth phase is in turn divided into five different phases derived from the Design Thinking process. These are Empathise, Define, Ideate, Prototype and Test. Each phase has a goal, a description of recurring bottlenecks, tips, and (co-creation) methods.

The methods given as examples for each phase are not all suitable for co-creation with the target group. Design thinking comes from product development in the commercial industry. Co-creation with the target group mainly takes place in the prototyping and testing phases. The first phases, where the problem is defined and ideas are developed, are usually done with the design team. The target group is only consulted for data collection, using interview and survey techniques. Therefore, there are fewer co-creation methods available for the early stages involving the target group.

Within CommuniCity, time and available financial resources limit the possibility to engage in a co-creation process that fully involves the target group as an equal partner. However, if we want to learn to design solutions that meet the needs of marginalised groups, there are a number of ways to incrementally improve the current process, in addition to the process described:

- A list of good practices in working with marginalised groups
- A workshop on co-creation for all pilot participants.
- A workshop on evaluating the proposals for the jury with detailed explanations on impact and co-creation.

The process itself is also open to improvement. Not only within CommuniCity but also beyond. The ambition is to develop the process into a toolbox that is open and accessible to anyone who wants to develop tech for and with marginalised groups. In addition, it should be possible to supplement this toolbox with new insights and methods that contribute to the involvement of marginalised groups in the design process and a better understanding of their position and challenge.

During our research, we came across four main bottlenecks that hinder the development of appropriate solutions for challenges faced by marginalised groups. We have so far focused on the second bottleneck that connects to the deliverable. The other three bottlenecks are not within the scope of this deliverable but do affect the process described:

1. Low awareness of the value of technology for social challenges.
2. Insufficient knowledge and understanding of the needs of marginalised groups.
3. Lack of funding for developing and purchasing tech solutions.
4. Few sustainable opportunities for implementation and maintenance.

We did search for solutions to these three remaining bottlenecks. In this deliverable, we provide suggestions and tips for further research and projects.

This deliverable describes a process and provides tools for involving marginalised groups in the development of technology solutions. The focus is on understanding the position of these target groups and the challenges they face. If we don't go into that, then applying a process and tools is useless. That is why this deliverable has a strong human side. It takes genuine interest and empathy to really develop solutions that meet the needs of marginalised groups. Our own intrinsic motivation to make a real difference to their situation is already half the success. We hope that the process in this deliverable will contribute to better engagement with marginalised groups, so that their experiences and ideas are at the heart of technology solutions that truly meet their needs and improve their position in society.

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CommuniCity First Round Pilots: <https://communicity-project.eu/pilots/>

Website Tech to the Rescue: <https://www.techtotherescue.org/>

Manual for conducting open calls: <https://manuals.communicity-project.eu/>

Open Data.ch. Hackathon handbook. <https://opendata.ch/handbook/#how?>

AMAI Vlaanderen: [amai!](http://amai.be)

OASC MIM5 Transparency: [MIM5 - Transparency - OASC MIMs \(oascities.org\)](http://mim5.org)

Tada City: <https://tada.city/>

Cities for digital rights: [Cities for Digital Rights](http://citiesfordigitalrights.org)

Toolboxes and sites of (co-creation) methods used in Chapter 5

Design Kit: <https://www.designkit.org/>

Think Design: <https://think.design/>

Unalab Enoll: <https://unalab.enoll.org/>

Design Method Toolkit: [Design Method Toolkit by the Digital Society School \(dss.cloud\)](http://dss.cloud)

Institute of Design at Stanford: [DESIGN-PROJECT-GUIDE-SEPT-2016-V3.pdf](http://design.stanford.edu)

University of Twente – Designlab: [Responsible-futuring/toolbox](http://designlab.utwente.nl)

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Value case methodologies mentioned in section 6.3.3 on value cases

The Most Significant Change: [Toolkit MSC manual for publication.pdf](#)

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